

**FINANCIAL ASSESSMENT OF PRIVATE SECTOR LIFE
AND NON-LIFE INSURERS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY
WITH REFERENCE TO FOREIGN DIRECT
INVESTMENT IN INDIA**

A Report

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*Declaration*_____

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the Report entitled “*Financial Assessment of Private Sector Life and Non-Life Insurers: A Comparative Study with Reference to Foreign Direct Investment in India*” submitted by **DR. TAMAL BASU** (Registration No.: 21SUPDR030) to **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow (PDF) under the Faculty of Management and Commerce, is a bonafide record of the research work carried out by him under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other Institute or University for the award of any degree or diploma.

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SYNOPSIS

In India, actually Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI) is the apex controller that supervises and regulates the insurance sector. IRDAI Act issues different guidelines from time to time in respect of allowing private companies in the life and non-life insurance sectors in India. Presently, Indian insurance industry has 57 insurance companies, where 24 are in the life insurance sector and 34 are in the non-life insurance sector. Among all the life insurers, only LIC, the public insurer and the remaining 23 companies are private insurers. In the non-life insurance segment, there are 6 public sector insurers in the non-life insurance segment and the rest 28 are private insurers. IRDAI published regulations in the year 2000 which notified the ceiling of investment to be made by the life and non-life insurers in exercising of the powers conferred in the Insurance Act, 1938. In the year 2000, after the representation of the IRDA Act, 1999 legalized the inflow of foreign shareholding (commonly known as FDI) only in the private life and non-life insurance companies to the extent of 26 per cent of the total shareholding. In the year 2015, the Government of India hiked the FDI capital in the private life and non-life insurers from 26 per cent to 49 per cent. FDI in insurance sector would be able to escalate the penetration of insurance in India and it can also be able to meet the long term capital requirements to fund the building of infrastructures in India. The present study makes an attempt to assess the financial performance in terms of return on equity, solvency, commission, operating expenses ratios, insured volumes and investment behaviour of the private sector insurers in the liberalized FDI inflows in life and non- life insurance in India. In addition, the study also evaluates the potency of FDI to increase profitability of the private sector insurers covering both life and non- life insurance or any one of them. Most of the previous studies have focused on the performance assessment with respect to profitability on few selected indicators and a small number of studies empirically tested the effect of FDI hike in life and non-life insurance sectors at aggregative level.

On the basis of the research gap the primary objective set in this study is to compare and assess the financial performance in terms of profitability, solvency, investment behaviour and service management of private sector insurers that are regulated by IRDA in Life and Non-Life Insurance at aggregative level with reference to FDI in India.

Semi-log regression model, Fisher's t Test, Chow test and Multivariate Regression Analysis (MRVA) have been employed in the study. It is observed that the growth rate

of all the financial instruments are positive and significant for both life and non-life insurers during the study period. However, the growth rate of investment income and annualized investment yield of the life insurers are negative, although insignificant and it is positive and statistically significant for the non-life insurers. Financial assessment in terms of prime earnings indicator and financial health indicator of life and non-life insurers, ROE (Return on Equity) shows positive but insignificant growth and SR (Solvency Ratio) shows negative significant growth which can't be treated as a favourable situation. However, OER (Operating Expenses Ratio) shows negative growth and FDIR (FDI inflow Ratio) growth is positive and significant, both of which is desirable. It is also noticed that CER (Commission Expenses Ratio) growth is higher for life insurers than that of the non-life insurers which reveals higher surplus for life insurance policy holders. The difference of mean of the performance indicator between life and non-life insurers in respect of ROE and FDIR are insignificant i.e., no difference in growth. However, for CER, OER, and SR, it is significant i.e., difference exists in growth.

From the year 2015, the changes in the FDI ceiling from 26% to 49% leads to the change in the structural break in the equity management and administration part for both life and non-life insurers and for that purpose, the difference in growth rates of the two sub periods has been analyzed. To get an overall idea, two regression equations have been formulated for two prime indicators i.e., ROE and SR as dependent variable and other earnings and financial health parameters as independent variable. The result is insignificant for both life and non-life insurers. In terms of revenue linked service indicator with respect to number of policies issued, the growth rate is better for non-life insurers than that of the life insurers since its growth is significant. The GRR (Grievances Resolved ratio) for both the insurers are desirable and almost 100%. But the changes in the ceiling of FDI and the change of management thereof shows a declining trend for life insurers from 2015. However, it has hardly any affect for non-life insurers.

ROE and SR can be regarded as prime financial indicator of the insurers in terms of profitability. The other earnings indicators (i.e., CER, OER, GRR, AIY, and FDIR) also have impact on ROE and SR. Here, the effect of FDIR is to be noticed on these variables to analyze the impact of FDI inflows on ROE and SR. For that purpose, MRVA has been performed with the inclusion of FDIR and exclusion of FDIR on prime performance parameter represented by ROE and SR. It shows insignificant

results for both the insurers i.e., FDI have no impact on these parameters during the study period.

Finally to conclude, it has been observed from the study that growth in the difference parameters is not desirable for both the insurers. The changes in the ceiling of FDI inflows and the overall impact of FDI during the study period on the performance parameter shows unsatisfactory results i.e., no impact is found for both the private life and non-life insurers. Somehow, in terms of investment management, a marginal better result is found for the non-life insurers.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AIY: Annualised Investment Yield
AOP: Association of Persons
AR: Automatic Route FIPB: Foreign Investment Promotion Board
CER: Commission Expenses Ratio
CFO: Chief Executive Officer
FDI: Foreign Direct Investment
FDIR: FDI Inflow
GIC Re: General Insurance Corporation of India
GRR: Grievances Resolved Ratio
HO: Head Office
IRDAI: Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India
KMP: Key Management Persons
LICI: Life Insurance Corporation of India
LPG: Liberalization, Privatization and Globalisation
MANOVA: Multivariate Analysis of Variance
MD: Managing Director
MVRA: Multivariate Regression Analysis
NRI: Non-Resident Indian
OER: Operating Expenses Ratio
PIO: Person of Indian Origin
PO: Principal Office
RBI: Reserve Bank of India
ROE: Return on Equity
SR: Solvency Ratio

CHAPTER- 1

INTRODUCTION

Chapter Outline:

- 1.1 Insurance Sector in India: An Overview***
- 1.2 Life and Non- Life Insurers in India***
- 1.3 Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI)
- A Synoptic Overview***
- 1.4 Investments by Life and Non-Life Insurers: Regulations of IRDAI***
- 1.5 Private Insurers of Life and Non-Life Insurance Sectors in India***
- 1.6 Foreign Direct Investment in Private Sector Insurers of India***
- 1.7 Statement of the Problem***
- 1.8 Chapter Plan***

Chapter – 1

Introduction

Financial Assessment is an evaluation procedure with the objective of any selected entity's ability to manage the funds so that it meets the justification of utilisation of funds which aligns the financial outcome of those funds. The process of financial assessment involves the following:

1. Capability of utilisation of own and outsider's funds.
2. Interpretation of relevant financial information from various sources.
3. Integration of non-financial information which directly and indirectly affects the financial outcomes.
4. Behavioural observations.
5. Financial capability.

Insurance is an intangible financial product used for safeguard against the risk of loss associated with aspects directly or indirectly related with life and related with financial activities. There are two parties in the insurance: one is insurer and other one is policy holder.

Insurer sold the intangible agreement known as insurance policy to the **Insured** i.e., policy holder against the consideration known as insurance premium.

The insurance sector is mainly classified into two groups i.e. life and non-life insurance.

Life Insurance is a contract between insurer and insured, where the insurer promises to pay a sum of money against a predetermined premium for a predetermined period upon the death of an insured person or at the end of that predetermined period.

Non-life insurance includes both people and things. Here the insurer provides financial protection to pay a sum of money against a predetermined premium associated with happening of any possible uncertain events which incurs loss for an insured person.

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is a route whereby people of one country can acquire full or partial ownership in capital or business assets for the purpose of monitoring the production, distribution and other activities of a business enterprise in another country.

1.1 INSURANCE SECTOR IN INDIA: AN OVERVIEW

The first legislation passed in India leading to all types of insurance to provide strict Government control over insurance business was the Insurance Act of 1938. After independence, life insurance business in India was wholly nationalized on 19th January 1956, through the Life Insurance Corporation Act passed by the Parliament. All the existing 245 insurance companies in the country, functioning on that time were amalgamated into one unit, the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LICI).

In the non- life insurance sector, General Insurance Business Act of 1972 was approved by the Indian Parliament through amalgamation of 107 general insurance companies operating on that time. After amalgamation four nationalized companies were formed which are as follows:

- i. National Insurance Company Limited,
- ii. New India Assurance Company Limited,
- iii. Oriental Insurance Company Limited, and
- iv. United India Insurance Company Limited.

In the life insurance sector, LICI had monopoly and in the non-life insurance sectors all the four nationalized companies shared the entire market as there were no private insurers allowed to act as insurance companies in India till 1990. In accordance with the recommendations of Malhotra Committee Report in the year 1999, the Government of India formed a sole regulating body, Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI) through passing an Act in the Parliament. In India, actually IRDAI is the apex controller that supervises and regulates the insurance sector. IRDAI Act issues different guidelines from time to time in respect of allowing private companies in the life and non-life insurance sectors in India.

1.2 LIFE AND NON- LIFE INSURERS IN INDIA

Presently, Indian insurance industry has 57 insurance companies, where 24 are in the life insurance sector and 34 are in the non-life insurance sector. Among all the life insurers, only LICI, the public insurer and the remaining 23 companies are private insurers. In the non-life insurance segment, there are 6 public sector insurers in the non-life insurance segment and the rest 28 are private insurers. Apart from these, there is a sole national re-insurer, namely General Insurance Corporation of India (GIC Re).

1.3 INSURANCE REGULATORY AND DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY OF INDIA (IRDAI) - A SYNOPTIC OVERVIEW

IRDAI is the sole regulator of insurance sector in India. The primary perseverance of IRDAI is to safeguard the interest of the policyholders and at the same time to confirm the growth of life and non-life insurance sectors.

The IRDAI Bill was passed in December 1999 and turn into an IRDAI Act in April 2000. The first meeting of the Insurance Advisory Committee of IRDAI held in July 2000 and 11 essential regulations relevant for private players entering into the Indian insurance market were recommended and accordingly formally notified. As per Sec. 4 of IRDAI Act, 1999, the member's composition of the IRDAI board is as follows:

- i. Chairman;
- ii. Five whole-time members;
- iii. Four part-time members (appointed by the Government of India).

The Head Office (HO) of the IRDAI is situated at Hyderabad and all the monitoring activities in respect of insurance regulations are carried out from the HO. The IRDAI has two regional Offices situated at New Delhi and Mumbai mainly concentrating on spreading policyholder's awareness and handling of their grievances. These offices are also functionally responsible for licensing of Surveyors and Loss Assessors specially related with non-life insurances.

IRDAI provides different regulatory activities in the following areas:

- i. Rules for the insurance industry for protecting the interests of the policyholder.
- ii. Rules and regulations in accordance with Section 114A of the Insurance Act of 1938.
- iii. Rules to grant certificates of registration for new insurance companies to be operated in India.
- iv. Rules to provide guarantee persistent with development of both the insurers and the policyholder.
- v. Rules to control and regulate insurance rates, policy terms and conditions, compensations offered by insurers to the policyholders.
- vi. Rules to undertake reviews and conduct audits of insurance companies, intermediary parties and other entities that are associated with the insurance business to control over misconducts.

- vii. Rules to grant licenses to insurance agents through required exam.
- viii. Rules to specify code of conduct, training and qualifications for various insurance agents.
- ix. Rules to address issues and provide resolutions in case of disputes which have arisen through ombudsman.
- x. Rules to regulate and control the rate of insurance to obstruct disagreeable and unnecessary price hikes in insurance premiums which might cause distress to the policyholders.
- xi. Rules for setting a minimum percentage limit of insurance companies for both life and non- life insurances to develop both rural as well as the urban sectors.
- xii. Rules for operational function of the Tariff Advisory Committee.
- xiii. Rules to states the procedures and methods in which books of accounts should be maintained and submitted by the insurers and insurance intermediaries.
- xiv. Rules for monitoring the investment of funds by insurance companies in accordance with the guidelines and administer the preservation of margin of solvency.
- xv. Rules for definite code of conduct to be followed by surveyors and loss assessors.

1.4 INVESTMENTS BY LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURERS: REGULATIONS OF IRDAI

IRDAI published Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (Investment) Regulations, 2000 as on 14th August, 2000 which notified the ceiling of investment to be made by the life and non-life insurers in exercising of the powers conferred under sections 27A, 27B, 27D and 114A of the Insurance Act, 1938.

Table - 1.1 and 1.2 shows the ceiling of investments to be made by life and non-life insurers respectively:

Table -1.1: Ceiling of Investments - Life Insurer

Sl.No	Types of Investment	Percentage
1	Central Government Securities	25% of Total Investments
2	State Government Securities or other approved securities including Sl. No. 1 above	Not less than 50% of Total Investments
3	Approved Investments (including Infrastructure and Social Sector)	Not less than 15% but not exceeding 35% of Total Investments
4	Other Approved Investments	Not exceeding 15% of Total Investments

Source: Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (Investment) Regulations, 2000 dated 14-08-2020

Table -1.2: Ceiling of Investments – Non- Life Insurer

Sl.No	Types of Investment	Percentage
1	Central Government Securities	20% of Total Investments
2	State Government Securities or other approved securities including Sl. No. 1 above	Not less than 30% of Total Investments
3	Housing funds and Loans to State Government for Housing along with Fire Fighting equipment	Not less than 5% of Total Investments
4	Approved Investments (including Infrastructure and Social Sector)	Not less than 10% but not exceeding 55% of Total Investments
5	Other Approved Investments	Not exceeding 25% of Total Investments

Source: Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (Investment) Regulations, 2000 dated 14-08-2020

1.5 PRIVATE INSURERS OF LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURANCE SECTORS IN INDIA

The entry route of allowing private insurance companies in India had begun at the early 1990s and in 1993. The Government of India set up R.N. Malhotra committee to provide necessary recommendations for entry norms of private companies. As an outcome of this report, the Insurance Regulatory and Development Act, 1999 (IRD Act) was passed by the Indian Parliament on 2nd December, 1999. The prime objective of this Act is to provide for the establishment of an authority which will formally allow the private players to enter into the insurance business in India. The IRDAI opened up the market for private players in August 2000 with formal invitation for application to get registration in life and non-life insurance business.

The private insurers in India are comparatively new and do not have a historical record, and thus general public frequently doubt or worried their reliability to invest in various life and non-life insurance products. A well-developed and grown insurance sector with participation from both private and public players are the key factors for economic development as it delivers a source of long- term funds for infrastructure development and strengthen the risk taking ability of the country. Following are the logics to clarify doubts and not feeling worried about investment in insurance products of the private insurers:

1. All these private insurance companies are regulated by the IRDAI.
2. All the life and non-life policies are to be launched and issued in accordance with the special guidelines of the IRDA in respect to private insurers.
3. IRDAI is a firm regulator and all insurance company operating in India has to abide by their rules and guidelines in respect of registration to winding up.
4. As per Section 64VA of the Insurance Act 1938, all the private insurers are required to maintain Solvency Margin of Rs 150 crores which needs to be submitted to the Reserve bank of India (RBI) under the administrative supervision of the IRDAI. It is basically treated as a safety deposit which is kept for repayment to customers in case of bankruptcy of the private insurers before disbursing out the claim of policyholders.
5. The Solvency Margin with RBI increases the portfolio of private insurance companies. Thus, even if the private insurer winds up their business and chooses to move out of India, RBI can be able to repay the claim of policyholders from the portfolio of security deposit that retain on behalf of the private insurers.
6. All the private insurance companies are associated with a Re-Insurance company who manage the obligation of repayment to policyholders in case of an extensive claim, if the insurer is incapable to pay.
7. For all the disputes between private insurers and policyholders, a formal approach can be made to Insurance Ombudsman which is a non-judicial authority to settle down disputes within the scope of certain financial limit and within a restricted timeframe. The judgment approved by the Ombudsman may be a binding on the part of the insurers but it does not restrict the policyholders. They have the option to go to the Consumer Forum

or the Court of Law upon dissatisfaction of judgments concluded by Ombudsman authority.

Thus, the trust on all the private insurers in India are governed by sufficient legal surroundings abides by laws. The financial performance of the private insurer has a great economic impact not only from the view point of the policyholders but also from the viewpoint of the long run sustenance of the Indian economy.

The private sector insurers (Life and non-life) registered with IRDAI as on 31st March 2020 are shown in **Appendix –A**.

1.6 FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN PRIVATE SECTOR INSURERS OF INDIA

In India, insurance sector first started the entry of private insurers in the year 2000 after the representation of the IRDA Act, 1999. This Act legalized the inflow of foreign shareholding commonly known as FDI only in the private life and non-life insurance companies to the extent of 26 per cent of the total shareholding. In the year 2015, the Government of India hiked the FDI capital in the private life and non-life insurers from 26 per cent to 49 per cent.

From the year 2000 i.e., when liberalization process in the insurance sector initiated, the public sector insurers dominated the insurance market as compared to the market share of the private insurers. But to increase the insurance penetration covering every corners of the country, management though FDI inflows especially in the private sector would play a better outcome. FDI in the private insurance sector would escalate the insurance penetration and can able to meet long term capital requirements in India for adequate funding in infrastructure sector. The private insurance sector has the ability of hovering long term investment from the common people so that it would indirectly provide assistance for growth of Indian economy. The advantages that can be identified in favour of permission of FDI inflows in the private insurance sectors are as follows:

- i. To enhance the investment avenues and associated income.
- ii. To generate new employment opportunity in accordance with the regulations of IRDAI.
- iii. To increase the chain of insurance services in the rural areas by providing variety of life and non-life insurance products.
- iv. To increase competition in insurance market and interrupt domestic monopolies.

- v. To increase revenue from direct and indirect tax of the Government.
- vi. To expedite the transfer of technology through implementation of foreign insurance service providing mechanism.
- vii. To encourage revolution in managerial skill through professional insurance service management.
- viii. To improve service quality in the rural areas and reduce cost of participations.
- ix. To increase insurance business outside India and decrease import service requirements.
- x. To affect the wave of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization (LPG), it will open many national private insurers for sweeping across the world with international players in the life and non-life insurance market.
- xi. To introduce diversified insurance products.
- xii. To manage insurance business with foreign investors in accordance with the regulator of the Govt. of India, so that protection of the national customers can be attained adequately.
- xiii. To capture and increase the penetration of Indian emerging insurance market as parallel to activities of public sector insurers.
- xiv. To introduce more competition in the insurance market and create new insurance market tending towards the free form of insurance market which may reduce the price or premium of the life and non-life policies as well as to augment the service quality of existing domestic insurers.

Finally, the private insurance companies which will be funded by the foreign players i.e., FDI mechanism in India will have more funds in their hands as well as lower cost of capital. Thus, efficiency results for the private insurance players may be favourable and expected better cover to the end of the policyholders in the coverage of formal regulator.

Table- 1.3 depicted the status of FDI inflows of private insurers as per the annual report of IRDAI for the year ended the 31st March, 2020.

Table – 1.3: Proportion of FDI inflows of Private Sector Insurers in India

Private Insurers	Total Number of Companies Registered with IRDAI	Number of Companies having no FDI inflows	Number of Companies having FDI inflows up to 26%	Number of Companies having FDI inflows up to 49%
Life Insurers	23	3	4	16
Non-Life Insurers	30	13	5	12
Total	53	16	9	28

Source: Annual Report of IRDAI-2019-20

The proportion of company-wise FDI inflows of private sector insurers (life and non-life) registered with IRDAI as on 31st March 2020 are shown in **Appendix –B**.

1.7 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Insurance sector plays a key role to mobilize national savings and channelize them into investments in diverse sectors of the economy. The insurance sector is mainly classified into two groups i.e., life and non-life insurance. Initially, after liberalization of the insurance sector, the public sector insurers continued to dictate the insurance market in India and covered around 90% of the market share. Apart from the life insurance sector, a rapid development has also been observed in the non-life insurance market which accounts for a substantial revenue growth in India. But the growth of proportions of insurance penetration is not favourable in the insurance sector. This may be due to the underperforming of private sector insurers or may be inefficient service management by the public sector insurers.

The contribution of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the present business environment around the world is remarkable. FDI in insurance sector would be able to escalate the penetration of insurance in India and it can also be able to meet the long term capital requirements to fund the building of infrastructures in India. Insurance sector has the ability of raising long-term capital from the common people, as it is the only path of investment where people put their money for as long as 20 years or even more. Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) of India as the sole regulator of insurance sector is in support for an increase in foreign equity capital through FDI inflows in the areas of insurance joint ventures, especially in the private sector insurers. The liberalization and globalization process in the insurance sector has

opened up many national markets for international business and better channelization of insurance services across the country. Presently, IRDA only allowed FDI in the private sector insurance in India.

The basic objective of the insurance sector is to increase the insurance penetration so that maximum number of people can be covered under insurable benefits to cope up with unavoidable circumstances. The necessity of both the types of insurance i.e., life and non-life has equal scope to handle the uncertain situations. So, as an insurance provider, the number of insurance policyholders and the quality of service in terms of grievances redressal are also very important to attain the basic objective of insurance.

The nature and scope of the two types of insurance sectors are different. However, as far the operational aspect of a company in terms of ownership is concerned; the two insurance sectors can be compared in terms of their financial performance.

In this framework, the present study makes an attempt to assess the financial performance in terms of return on equity, solvency, commission, operating expenses ratios, insured volumes and investment behaviour of the private sector insurers in the liberalized FDI inflows in life and non- life insurance in India. In addition, the study also evaluates the potency of FDI to increase profitability of the private sector insurers covering both life and non- life insurance or any one of them.

1.8 CHAPTER PLAN

1. Introduction
2. Literature Review
3. Research Methodology
4. FDI in Insurance Sector: An Overview
5. Financial Performance of Private Life and Non-Life Insurers: A Comparative Analysis
6. FDI in Insurance Sector: Impact on Financial Performance of Private Life and Non-Life Insurers
7. Summary, Conclusions and Suggestions

CHAPTER- 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Chapter Outline:

- 2.1 *Studies on Life Insurance Sector***
- 2.2 *Studies on Non-Life Insurance Sector***
- 2.3 *Studies on Life and Non-Life Insurance Sectors***
- 2.4 *Discovery of Research Gap***

Chapter – 2

Literature Review

Contemporary literature highlights a number of major concepts and findings regarding performance assessment of insurance sectors with special reference to Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in India. Some of the existing literatures on performance assessment of life and non-life insurance sectors that are available from various sources are reviewed here. Finally, on the basis of the review, the research gap is identified for the present study.

2.1 STUDIES ON LIFE INSURANCE SECTOR

1. **Ramesh Lal (2002)**, in his thesis “**Divisional performance evaluation of LIC business in north zone**”, identified the problems regarding the liquidation risk, ratings of the insurer and outstanding elements which leads to the underperformance of LIC business in the northern region of India.
2. **Goswami (2007)**, in his paper “**Customer Satisfaction with Service Quality in the Life Insurance Industry in India**” identified that before the initiation of the entry of private players of life insurance sector, Life Insurance Corporation of India (LICI) was the single player in India. The study showed that within six years from the entry of private players in the Indian life insurance market, LICI has lost 29% market share, although market size and the amount of insurance premium collected had been raised for LICI along with private players.
3. **Shrinivas (2008)**, in his paper “**Causes of Lapsation of Life Insurance Policies in Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India**” indicated the reasons behind declining growth in new insurance policies of LICI after privatization across the country. The areas suggested for underperforming of LICI were related with the functioning of branch managers, development officers and all types of insurance agents who were the main promoting staff for LICI as compared to the private insurers.
4. **Bedi and Singh (2011)**, in their paper “**An Empirical Analysis of Life Insurance Industry in India**” analysed an inclusive performance of life insurance sectors of India between pre- and post-economic reforms period. The study period covered from 1980 to 2009. The empirical results found an incredible growth in the performance of both public and private life insurance

sectors due to the policy of LPG. The nature of insurance industry also upgraded due to the opening up of foreign players in private sector insurers. It was also observed from the study that there was a significant change in the investment pattern of LIC.

5. **Kumari, (2013)** in his paper “**Performance Evaluation of Indian Life Insurance Industry in post Liberalization**” evaluated the performance of Indian private and public life insurance industries with various ratios. The study showed an increase in insurance penetration and density due to opening up the private sector insurance players. The performance of different ratios was found to be favourable to express the financial stability of the insurers.
6. **Mishra, (2015)** in his study “**A Comparative Study of Public and Private Life Insurance Companies in India**” conducted a comparative study between public and private sector life insurance companies in India with some selected parameters like market share, new business premium, number of new policies issued and total life insurance premium underwritten. The results found that for all the selected parameters, LIC accounted a dominating player. The study also concluded that the private insurance companies have to ensure more quality products with a competitive premium by reducing their operational cost and also provide better service quality to increase their profitability and productivity performance.
7. **Gairola, (2016)** in his study “**A Comparative Study of Public and Private Life Insurance Companies in Post Liberalization Era**” showed a comparison with respect to new policies issued; total premium income and market share. The study found that private life insurers had created a competitive environment which affected the performance of LIC in many ways. The study also showed the initiatives like introduction of new and attractive insurance plans that took by the LIC to overcome and compete with that situation.
8. **Yadav and Mohania (2016)** in their paper “**Impact of F.D.I on Life Insurance Sector in India**” explained that insurance industry in India is still less penetrated but the growth potential is very high on the basis of the secondary data collected from I.R.D.A and research papers from various journals. The study concluded that an increase in FDI showed a positive move for the future of Life Insurance Sector in India. The study suggested that as the

insurance sector needs huge amount of capital investment, it can be done effectively only through the increase in FDI which leads to the enhancement of the overall performance of life insurance sector.

9. **Gowda and Kantha (2016)**, in their paper “**Foreign Direct Investment in Indian Insurance Industry - An Analytical Study**” analysed the significance of FDI in public and private life insurance industries in India. The study concluded that FDI in life insurance may bring product modernization and technological improvement but at the same time it brings an overabundance of risks. An unnecessary escalation in the number of private players in the industry will certainly expose the country into risks. It is suggested that policy makers and regulatory body i.e., IRDA have the utmost role to play in this regard as increase in scope of foreign holding should not be exposed to all types insurers. It is recommended that there should be some eligible conditions and strategies towards relaxing FDI policies in life insurance sector.
10. **Badla, and Tandon, (2017)** in their article “**Profitability Performance of Life Insurance Companies- A Study in Indian Context**” showed performance of life insurance companies in India in the context of profitability using seven variables such as net premium received, income from investments, underwriting income, ROA, ROCE, solvency ratio and PAT. The empirical results found that among the selected private sector companies, ICICI prudential accounted the highest average net premium received and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of investment income during the last 5 years of the study period. The CAGR of underwriting income had showed declined trends for all the private sector life insurance companies during the last 5 years of the study period. The study suggested that most of the private life insurers in India are required to have a sound management to control expense ratio and other outflows to make higher profitability.
11. **Patel and Dwiveli, (2019)** in their paper “**A Comparative Study of Public and Private Sector Life Insurance Companies in India: Post Liberalization Span**” analysed how liberalization had made impact on life insurance sector for a study period of 17 years. The study also compared the performance of public and private life sector insurance companies in India during the post liberalization period with a sample size of 24 companies. The

study concluded that during the liberalization period, India had reported a significant increase in life insurance density, penetration, premium collection and number of policies.

12. **Kanzal, and Harsha, (2021)** in their paper “**Impact of FDI on Insurance Sector in India with Special Reference to SBI Life Insurance**” examined the impact of FDI on SBI Life Insurance Company Limited on the basis of the primary data by consulting with the officials and policyholders. The secondary data also collected from the reports are available in the websites. The study concluded that FDI played a significant role in life insurance industry that accounted a good growth in FDI participation. It also showed in the study that there was an improvement in quality of service rendered to the policy holders of SBI Life Insurance Company Limited.

2.2 STUDIES ON NON-LIFE INSURANCE SECTOR

1. **Mahal (2002)**, in the article on “**Assessing Private Health Insurance in India: Potential Impacts and Regulatory Issues**”, identified that entry of private sector health insurers in India were expected to have an influence on the costs and quality of health care. Private equity in financing also affected the cost-effectiveness of healthcare sector. However, proper regulatory norms with approved bodies like IRDA had impact of healthcare packages linked with health care. New legislative standards could improve the performance of private health insurance sector.
2. **Raman (2004)**, in his study “**Regulatory Dissonance and Challenges to Globalization: A Comparative Study of the United States and Indian Non-life Insurance Regulatory Frameworks**” identified the regulatory difference that existed in the non- life insurance industry between the U.S. and India. It was highlighted theoretically in the areas of regulatory disagreement in the non- life insurance business such as definition area of products, treatment of acquisition outlays, treatment of unearned premiums, creation of a calamity reserve, reinsurance cession, investment regulation, responsibilities to the rural sectors, compulsion on social sectors, formation regulations and guidelines on solvency position.
3. **Sinha (2007)**, in his paper “**Productivity and Efficiency of Indian General Insurance Industry**” analysed that the public sector general insurance companies lead the private sector general insurance companies in context of

mean technical efficiency on selected parameters in constant returns to scale, while the private general insurance companies had marginally higher mean technical efficiency on selected parameters than that of the public general insurance companies in variable returns to scale.

4. **Shreedevi and Manimegalai (2013)**, in their paper “**A Comparative Study of Public and Private Non- Life Insurance Companies in India**” conducted a comparative study based on the parameters like number of new policies issued, gross direct premium and net incurred claims based on secondary data during the period 2002-03 to 2010-11. Empirical results found significant difference in growth with respect to all the parameters among the public and private non-life insurers and showed that public sectors companies had done well because of their aggressive pricing and holding of existing customers.
5. **Sinha and Bandopadhyay (2015)**, in their article “**An Analysis of Efficiency of General Insurance Industry in India**” determined the efficiency of the non-life private and public insurance sectors using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) on the basis of the secondary data for the period 2004-05 to 2011-12. The empirical results showed that inefficiency percentage in all the sectors was fairly low and all the insurers had performed well in the insurance industry, but in terms of technical and pure technical efficiency, the overall result of the public sector insurers beats the private insurers.
6. **Pakira (2015)**, in his paper “**Growth Performance Analysis -A Comparative Study between Private and Public Sector Non-Life Insurance Companies**” compared the growth performance of performance indicators such as Gross Direct Premium Income, No of Policies Issued, Incurred Claims Ratio, Change in Reserve for Unexpired Risk, Commission, Expenses of Management, Equity Share Capital of Non-Life Insurers and Net Profit After Tax at aggregative level during the period 2001-02 to 2013-14. The empirical results of the study concluded that public sector non-life insurance companies had performed superior than the private sector non-life insurance companies in terms of all the selected parameters.
7. **Rajeev (2016)**, in his study “**Impact of Foreign Direct Investment in the Indian General Insurance Sector**” showed the pattern, recent trends and effect of FDI in the general insurance sector of India on the basis of secondary data during the period 2006 to 2014. The empirical results showed a

growth in number of policies issued, premium income and equity shares of foreign investors of the general insurance sector during the study period. The study suggested that quality, range, variety and price of different general insurance products had pointedly improved. It was also suggested that the foreign insurers had arrived through a joint venture route so that their entry into the insurance segment had generated a tough competition among the public and private general insurance sector.

8. **Anupreeta, (2018)**, in his paper “**Health Insurance in India-A Comparative Study of Public and Private Companies Regarding Service Cost**” conducted a comparison between Public and Private Insurers in respect to the service quality with primary as well as some secondary data. The study found that the selected sample health insurance sector companies had performed well in most of the selected parameters but they failed to reach the expectation of the policyholders in some service related areas. It was also observed that the variety of health insurance products in private sector insurers was quite large in comparison to public sector insurers and they followed more tailor made shape to serve their customers. The study suggested that the Public sector insurers should escape the rigidity and required to focus on enhancing the range of products and accordingly to get ready for molding the insurance policies. It was also recommended that health insurance products should be flexible, affordable in context to the amount of premium, health benefits and suitable the need of the policyholders.
9. **Joshi and Kohli (2018)**, in their article “**Comparative Evaluation of performance of FDI based and Non FDI based Non-Life Insurance companies**” compared the financial performance on selected parameters in respect of FDI based and non FDI based non-Life Insurance companies in India. Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Reinsurance and Actuarial practices were selected as performance parameters of non-life insurance sector during the period of study 2004 to 2016. The empirical results concluded that in most of the selected parameters, FDI based companies performed superior than non-FDI companies in non-life insurance sector.
10. **Surya, Sudha, and Priyanka (2019)**, in their study “**FDI in Indian Non-Life Insurance Sector: Boost Market Potential**” examined the performance of Non-life Insurance sector in India after the hike of FDI limit in India from 26

percent to 49 percent (Notified as on 16 March 2016) for the years 2016-17 and 2017-18. Basic parameters used in the study were number of insurers, insurance penetration and profit after tax. The study found a growth in the insurance penetration, density and total premium collection of Indian non-life insurance sector. The article suggested that active participation of foreign investors would be very important and it would bring dynamic practices environment in the non-life insurance sector.

2.3 STUDIES ON LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURANCE SECTORS

1. **Rao (2000)**, in his paper “**The Indian Insurance Industry the Road Ahead**” explained that Indian life and non-life insurance market is still immature. It had a huge growth potential in terms of penetration, especially in the rural areas where growth had so far remained slow.
2. **Goyal (2004)**, in his paper “**Growth of Private Insurance companies**” indicated that private sector insurance companies in India had get motivated after implementation of diverse insurance products through investment by foreign investors. The study suggested that the performance of private insurance sector will be affected by the increase of eligibility of foreign investors from 26 percent to 49 per cent as per the Union Budget 2004-05.
3. **Ray and Pathak (2006)**, in their article “**Strategizing the Exposure Mix in Various Communication Channels for Enhancing Visibility in the Indian Insurance Industry**” showed that privatization of the insurance sector in India since 2000 had witnessed the involvement of various private players, mostly through joint venture agreement between foreign insurance players. The study suggested that exposure and communication channel of private insurance players had diversified to a new road map in Indian life and non-life insurance markets.
4. **Shikhare (2015)**, in his paper “**Foreign direct investment in insurance sector in India**” analysed the benefits of increased FDI limit in the life and non-life insurance sectors based on secondary data. The study suggested that excess increase of foreign capital may lead to the option of exposing the economy to the vulnerabilities of the global insurance market by means of inheritance of unsound balance sheets and financial health of some foreign partners through joint ventures agreement and subsidiary routes flight the capital outside of the country and also threatening the interest of the policy

holders. It was recommended that any additional hike in FDI at this stage may not be in the interest of the Indian life and non-life insurance sector, whereby the common man too would not stand to gain through insurance, mostly as a means of social security.

5. **Hasan (2015)**, in his article “**Impact Analysis of FDI on Insurance Sector in India**” emphasized the framework of the Indian life and non-life insurance sectors along with the opportunities and major challenges due to the increase of FDI in Indian private insurance sector. The study concluded that necessary time to the regulatory changes in the insurance sector would be important for the future progress of insurance industry and active foreign participation in equity is vital for the sector as it would bring the best know how and applying the best service practices. It was also suggested in the study that there is also a risk in FDI that unless it gives the management control in Indian companies, the foreign insurance companies would be reluctant to invest in India.
6. **Soni (2017)**, in his study “**Impact of Foreign Direct Investment in India on Insurance Industry**” analysed the impact, problems and Government policies of FDI in insurance sector. The study concluded that enhancement of F.D.I was an optimistic change for the future of Indian Insurance Sector since the CAGR of this sector showed a significant growth. The study suggested that the increase of capital investment through increase in FDI in insurance sector will enhance the overall performance in terms of profitability and insurance penetration.
7. **Gattaiah (2017)**, in his paper “**Impact of FDI on Insurance Sector in India – An Analytical Study**” analyzed the performance of public and private life and non-life insurance companies and identified the significance of FDI in insurance sector in India based on secondary data during the period 2004-05 to 2011-12. The study found a significant growth in insurance penetration and new insurance offices have been extended to rural area in India to offer insurance exposure among low and average income people. The public life insurance company i.e. LIC was continuous to dominate the market by maintaining stability in its growth rate. For non- life insurance companies there was an augmented rate of growth in collection of insurance premium both for public and private companies and competitive environment has created for public general insurance companies in India. But private players

for both life and non-life insurance showed improvement in their market share. The study suggested that IRDA had to play an important role to administer and to regulate insurance business in the context of FDI arena to protect the interest of policy holders and other stakeholders in India.

8. **Pavithra and Ramu (2018)**, in their paper “**A Study on the Impact of FDI in Insurance Sector**” indicated the issues of FDI inflows in Indian insurance sector and explore benefits of expanded outside direct venture in insurance to confine the protection segment of policyholders. The paper also discussed the Government arrangement with respect to protection division in respect to the issues of FDI in Insurance Sector.
9. **Jha (2018)**, in his article “**Role of FDI in Indian Insurance Sector**” showed a scenario and scope of FDI for progress of insurance sector in India and also indicated the Government initiatives through regulatory bodies regarding FDI in insurance sector. The study suggested that the role of overseas capital could create an opportunity of exposing the insurance sector, but heavy reliance on foreign partners could be the cause of unsound financial fitness and capital flights outside the country which ultimately affect the interest of the policy holders.
10. **Jose (2019)**, in his study “**An Analytical Study of Privatisation in Indian Insurance Sector**” analysed the pros and cons of privatization in Indian insurance sector on the basis of secondary data. The study also showed the different aspects of insurance characteristics and overall activities after privatization. It was concluded that privatization of insurance sector somehow decrease the monopoly of the public sector but both private and public sector became competitive to provide better services to the new customers along with existing customers.
11. **Sandhu and Kaur (2019)**, in their article “**Brunt of FDI on Insurance Sector**” assessed the impact of FDI on life and non-life insurance sectors of India based on the secondary data during the period from 2012-13 to 2016-17. The study concluded that there was a positive impact on equity share capital and collection of insurance premium for both life and non-life insurance sectors. ULIP policies of life insurance sector and central government securities of non-life insurance sector had shown a negative impact. The

profitability of life insurance sector and investment of non-life insurance sector showed positive impact due to FDI inflows in insurance sector.

2.4 DISCOVERY OF RESEARCH GAP

The objective of any researcher is to identify the research gap with profound understanding to avoid repeating existing research and establish an original thought to provide output for the users in that field for their future course of actions.

From the literature review as stated above, it is found that a study carried out by **Shreedevi and Manimegalai**²⁷ in the year **2013** compared the performance of public and private insurance companies in the non-life sector at aggregate level during the FDI period with respect to 'Number of New Policies Issued', 'Gross Direct Premium' and 'Net Incurred Claim Ratio'. Moreover, the study showed only year by year growth of the selected parameters.

Another study was conducted by **Pakira, S.K**¹⁸ in the year **2015** that conducted a comparative assessment of public and private non –life insurance companies at aggregate level with respect to the selected parameters like 'Gross Direct Premium Income', 'Number of Policies Issued', 'Incurred Claims Ratio', 'Change in Reserve for Unexpired Risk', 'Commission Expenses of Management', 'Equity Share Capital of Non-Life Insurers', and 'Net Profit After Tax'.

Both these studies have made comparison between public and private sector insurers at aggregative level and considered only non-life insurance sectors. Till date, FDI inflows are not permissible in public life and non- life insurance sectors in India. Therefore, performance assessment of private life and non-life insurance during the FDI period and the impact in financial performance due to change in the norms of FDI hike is required to be assessed. Hence, these aspects are missing in the above two studies.

From the review of literatures as stated above, the following research gaps are identified:

1. Few studies are carried out in the context of scope of FDI and strategies adopted by Government. Hence, these studies are theoretical in nature.
2. Majority of the studies have been carried out in the context of only insurance penetration of life or non- life or both life and non- life after the implementation of FDI approvals.

3. Majority of the studies made a comparison with respect to impact of FDI between Public and Private Insurers, although FDI inflows are not yet permissible in the public sector in India.
4. Most of the previous studies have focused on the performance assessment with respect to profitability on few selected indicators within life insurance companies or within non-life insurance companies.
5. Few studies have concentrated on the assessment of solvency position of life and non- life insurance sectors at aggregative level after introduction of FDI inflows in India.
6. A small number of studies empirically tested the effect of FDI hike in life and non-life insurance sectors at aggregative level.
7. Majority of the studies have made a comparative assessment at disaggregate level i.e., company-wise analysis between public and private life and non-life insurance sectors during the FDI period. Therefore, we hardly get any idea about the impact of FDI in the private insurance sector where FDI is permissible in India.
8. Very few studies have focused on the service management of the private insurance sectors during FDI periods in the context of number of insurance policies issued, insurance penetration and status of grievances linked with financial performance. Therefore, we scarcely get any idea about the service quality of the private insurance companies due to the change of ownership pattern and management in the FDI arena.
9. Few studies are attempted to analyze the growth of investment behavior and investment income of private life and non-life insurance companies at aggregative level during the FDI period.

CHAPTER- 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Chapter Outline:

- 3.1 Research Objectives***
- 3.2 Hypotheses of the Study***
- 3.3 Sample Selection***
- 3.4 Data Source***
- 3.5 Study Period***
- 3.6.1: Ratio Analysis of Financial Performance Indicators***
- 3.6.2: Estimation of Trend Growth Rates***
- 3.6.3: Fisher's t Test***
- 3.6.4: Chow test***
- 3.6.5: Multivariate Regression Analysis***

Chapter – 3

Research Methodology

In this chapter, the research objectives based on the research gap identified in chapter - 2, hypotheses of the study, tools and techniques to carry out the study have been described. Apart from this, sample selection, data source, and study period have also been discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to compare and assess the financial performance in terms profitability, solvency, investment behaviour and service management of Private Sector Insurers regulated by IRDA in Life and Non-Life Insurance at aggregative level with reference to Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in India. To achieve this primary objective, the following secondary objectives are required to be achieved:

1. To compare and examine the profitability and solvency position on the basis of selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life insurers.
2. To compare and examine the investment behaviour of private Life and Non-Life insurers.
3. To compare and examine the service management on the basis of selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life insurers.
4. To examine the impact of FDI hike on the financial performance of private life and non-life insurers.
5. To identify whether the FDI inflows have any major impacts towards improving the financial performance parameters of the private Life and Non-Life insurers.

3.2 Hypotheses of the Study

1st Hypothesis:

H_{O1}: There has been no significant growth in selected financial performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers

H_{A1}: H_{O1} is not true.

2nd Hypothesis:

H_{O2}: There is no significant difference in average financial performance with respect to selected performance parameters between private Life and Non-Life Insurers.

H_{A2}: H_{O2} is not true.

3rd Hypothesis:

H_{O3}: There is no significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study.

H_{A3}: H_{O3} is not true.

4th Hypothesis:

H_{O4}: FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers.

H_{A4}: H_{O4} is not true.

3.3 Sample Selection: The study considers all the private life and non-life insurance companies that are operating in India and 10 years data has been selected.

3.4 Data Source: The data have been collected mainly from secondary sources, i.e., from the website of IRDA and from the published Annual Reports of IRDA.

3.5 Study Period: The period under study ranges over ten years from 2010-11 to 2019-20. The reason for selection of this study period is due to a substantial hike in FDI norms in the year 2015.

3.6 Tools and Techniques of the Study:

3.6.1: Ratio Analysis of Financial Performance Indicators: In support of literature review and the financial indicator of the life and non-life insurers, we have identified the following widely used financial ratios and used in our study:

- ROE (Return on Equity),
- CER (Commission Expenses Ratio),
- OER (Operating Expenses Ratio),
- SR (Solvency Ratio), and
- FDIR (FDI Inflow Ratio).

$$\text{ROE} = \frac{\text{Net Profit after Tax}}{\text{Indian Equity Capital} + \text{FDI Equity Capital} + \text{Reserve \& Surplus}}$$

The ROE is a measure of profitability of the life and non-life insurers in relation to the funds supplied by the Indian and FDI stakeholders and owners taken together. Return on equity measures entirely the return on the owner's resources.

$$\text{CER} = \frac{\text{Commission Paid}}{\text{Gross Premium Collected}}$$

CER reflects the outflow towards total commission expense as compared with the gross premium collected during a financial year of the insurance company. Lower the commission expenses, the healthier for the insurance company.

$$\text{OER} = \frac{\text{Total Management Expenses}}{\text{Gross Premium Collected}}$$

OER is a measure of the total management expense i.e., commission, operational and administrative expenses in relation to the gross premium collected. This is the cost that insurance company deducts from the policy holders which reduces investment return both for the policy holders and insurers. Lower the OER, it is beneficial for the insurers.

$$\text{SR} = \frac{\text{Net Income} + \text{Depreciation}}{\text{Total Debt Obligation}}$$

SR measures the insurer's ability to settle the claims or financial capacity to meet its policy holder's obligations. A high ratio refers that the insurer is financially capable and it has sufficient funds to pay all valid claims. According to the IRDAI's guideline's, the minimum solvency ratio to be maintained by the insurers is 1.5 to maintain lower risks. So in relations of solvency margin, the mandatory value must be 150%.

$$\text{FDIR} = \frac{\text{FDI Capital}}{\text{Total Capital}}$$

It is a measure of total inflow of FDI inflows in the capital structure as compared to the total capital. The ceiling of FDI upto 2015 is 26%, after that it is 49%. So this ratio indicates the use of FDI capital subject to constraint of its maximum limit. Higher FDIR indicates the better use of foreign equity.

3.6.2: Estimation of Trend Growth Rates: To calculate the trend growth rates of the selected performance indicators, semi-log trend equation has been used in the study. The semi-log model has been selected since it gives the growth rate directly at a point of time.

Semi- log trend line equation:

$$\text{Log } Y = a + bt + U_t$$

Where: Y represents dependent variable, a represents constant, b represents growth rate (beta co-efficient), t represents time, and U_t represents random disturbance term. In our study, Y indicates performance indicators in terms of Investment in Central Government Securities, Investment in State Government Securities, Investment in Housing & Infrastructure, Investment in Housing funds and Loans to State Government for Housing along with Fire Fighting equipment, Approved Investments, Other Investments, Investment Income, Annualized Investment Yield, Return on Equity (ROE), Commission Expenses Ratio (CER), Operating Expenses Ratio (OER), Solvency Ratio (SR), FDI Inflow Ratio (FDIR), Number of New Policies Issued, Grievances Reported During the Year and Grievances Resolved Ratio (GRR).

3.6.3: Fisher's t Test: As in our study, the sample size is less than 30, we have employed Fisher's t Test to test the difference of mean of selected performance indicators between Private Life Insurers (aggregative) and Private Non-Life Insurers (aggregative).

The 't' statistic is defined as:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{y}_1}{s \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}}}$$

Where n_1 = Sample size of Private Life Insurers

n_2 = Sample size of Private Non-Life Insurers

$\bar{x}_1$ = Mean of Performance Indicator of Private Life Insurers

$\bar{y}_1$ = Mean of Performance Indicator of Private Non-Life Insurers

s_1^2 and s_2^2 are the variances of the sample of Private Life Insurers and Private Non-Life Insurers respectively.

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{n_1 s_1^2 + n_2 s_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}$$

Degree of Freedom = $n_1 + n_2 - 2$

If the observed value is greater than table value (t value), then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is significant difference between two means, while we accept null hypothesis if the observed value is smaller than the tabulated value.

3.6.4 Chow test: This model uses F-test to determine whether a single regression is more efficient than two separate regressions involving splitting of the data into two sub-samples. This indicates whether in the second case we have a structural break at 't' point of time or not. The null hypothesis in this model is structural stability. If we reject null hypothesis; it means we have a structural break in the data.

$$F = \frac{RSS_c - (RSS_1 + RSS_2) / k}{RSS_1 + RSS_2 / n - 2k}$$

Where: RSS_c = Residual Sum of Square of Combined Observations

RSS_1 = Residual Sum of Square of Pre Break Observations

RSS_2 = Residual Sum of Square of Post Break Observations

n = Number of Observations, k = Number of Breaks

$n = n_1$ (Number of Pre Break Observations) + n_2 (Number of Post Break Observations)

Degree of Freedom = $n_1 + n_2 - 2k$

3.6.5 Multivariate Regression Analysis: The model is similar to linear regression, except that it accommodates more than one independent variable. In short it is a method that estimates a solo regression model with multiple outcome variables. The equation for a multiple regression can be expressed by this equation:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where y is the dependent variable, x_i is the independent variable, and β_i is the coefficient for the independent variable. This equation finds the association between the dependent variable and each independent variable, while calculating for all other variables.

The results found from running the equation are as follows:

- R Squared: It is the proportion of variability of the dependent variable that can be expressed by the independent variables in the model.

- **Adjusted R Squared:** It is the R Squared value, but with a consequence on the number of independent variables used in the model. The R Squared value can only increase with the addition of more factors in the model, the model will just ignore the fresh factor if it does not assist clarify the dependent variable.
- **Coefficients** It is the change in the number of units of the dependent variable associated with an increase of 1 unit of the independent variable, controlling for the other independent variables.
- **P Value:** It is the value is the statistical significance of the coefficient. By comparing the p value to the alpha (typically 0.05), we can determine whether or not the coefficient is significantly different from the weight of null hypothesis i.e. 0. An independent variable with a statistically insignificant aspect may not be important to the model.

Interpretation of Multivariate Regressions

- The coefficients may or may not be statistically significant
- The coefficients hold true on average
- The coefficients involve relationship not causation
- The coefficients organize for other factors

CHAPTER- 4

FDI IN INSURANCE SECTOR: AN OVERVIEW

Chapter Outline:

- 4.1 Automatic Route: Meaning***
- 4.2 Eligible Investors of FDI in Insurance Sector***
- 4.3 Eligible Investee Entities of FDI in Insurance Sector***
- 4.4 FDI in Insurance Sector through Automatic Route***
- 4.5 FDI: Repatriation Option of Investment***
- 4.6 Investment in Insurance Sector by Eligible Non-Residents Investees other than NRIs/PIO***
- 4.7 Compliance under IRDA Act, 1999 with respect to Insurance Companies***
- 4.8 Indian Owned and Controlled Guidelines with respect to FDI: An Overview***

Chapter – 4 FDI in Insurance Sector: An Overview

In this chapter, the route, ceiling eligibility, and conditions of FDI investment in private insurance sector have been described.

4.1 AUTOMATIC ROUTE: MEANING

The term Automatic Route (AR) refers that a foreign investor who is willing to invest and the Indian company who is willing to take investment from foreign investor does not require any previous approval from the Reserve Bank or Government of India to deal with that business arrangements. Actually, the sector specific ceiling of approval in respect to the automatic route of FDI is specified under the consolidated FDI Policy of India. The ceiling of this route may be changed by the Government in respect to the proposals of Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) or Cabinet Committee on Economic Affairs or Cabinet Committee on Securities.

4.2 ELIGIBLE INVESTORS OF FDI IN INSURANCE SECTOR

Following are the conditions to attain the eligibility for FDI:

- The entity must be a non-resident in India.
- The citizen of Bangladesh and Pakistan or an entity incorporated under any Act of Bangladesh and Pakistan can be able to invest only through the Government route.
- NRIs resident and citizens of Nepal and Bhutan are permitted to invest but not through automatic route.
- Entities having adverse notice of RBI cannot be able to make new investments under FDI Policy through automatic route without having the prior approval from concerned authorities.
- A company, trust, and partnership firm incorporated outside India and owned and controlled by NRIs can be able to invest in India in accordance with the special dispensation rules under FDI Policy.

4.3 ELIGIBLE INVESTEE ENTITIES OF FDI IN INSURANCE SECTOR

Following are the conditions to attain the eligibility for investee entities under FDI:

- The company must be an Indian Company.
- A Person of Indian Origin (PIO) or a Non-Resident Indian (NRI) residing outside India can invest in the capital of a firm or a proprietary concern in India on repatriation basis i.e., not in automatic route. In this respect, the amount should be

invested though inward remittance maintained out of NRE/ FCNR (B)/NRO account maintained with Authorized Dealers/Authorized banks. The firm or proprietary concern should not engaged in any type of agricultural/plantation or real estate business or print media sector.

4.4 FDI IN INSURANCE SECTOR THROUGH AUTOMATIC ROUTE

The ceiling of equity investment by the eligible investors in the eligible investees of the insurance sectors is shown in Table 4.

Table 4.1: FDI Ceiling in Insurance Sector

Companies	Before Insurance Laws (Amendment) Act 2015	After Insurance Laws (Amendment) Act 2015	Route of Entry
Life and Non-life Insurance Companies	26% of Total Equity Capital	49% of Total Equity Capital	Automatic
Insurance Brokers Companies	26% of Total Equity Capital	49% of Total Equity Capital	Automatic
Third Party Administrators Companies relating to insurance	26% of Total Equity Capital	49% of Total Equity Capital	Automatic
Surveyors and Loss Assessors Companies relating to insurance	26% of Total Equity Capital	49% of Total Equity Capital	Automatic
Other Insurance companies acted as Intermediaries appointed under the provisions of Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Act, 1999 (41 of 1999)	26% of Total Equity Capital	49% of Total Equity Capital	Automatic

Source: <https://www.irdai.gov.in/>

In Table 4, the total foreign equity investment in automatic route shall be computed in accordance with Regulation 11 of Rule 2 (P) of the IRDAI (Registration of Indian Insurance Companies) Regulations, 2000.

4.5 FDI: REPATRIATION OPTION OF INVESTMENT

A Person of Indian Origin (PIO) or a Non-Resident Indian (NRI) willing to invest in the insurance sector not covered under automatic route of investment are required to pursue an application with all prescribed documents to RBI to get aforementioned permission of FDI investment in any sole proprietorship concerns or partnership firms engaged in insurance activities. The grant of investment will be decided based on the

application by RBI with consultation of appropriate authorities of the Government of India. This process is known as repatriation option of investment in FDI.

4.6 INVESTMENT IN INSURANCE SECTOR BY ELIGIBLE NON-RESIDENTS INVESTEEES OTHER THAN NRIS/PIO

Any person who is a resident of outside India not covered under NRIs/PIO category may sort for an application of FDI investment in insurance sector. For that purpose he need to get prior approval from Reserve Bank with requisite formalities with detailed plan of making investment in the capital of a firm or a proprietorship concern or any Association of Persons (AOP) engaged in business of insurance activities or any association of persons in India as automatic route is not permitted in this case. These persons need to follow the procedure of investment covered under repatriation option of investment in FDI with some specific clause of investments of NRIs. In this case, the permission also grant with consultation between Government of India and the appropriate authorities engaged for that purpose.

4.7 COMPLIANCE UNDER IRDA ACT, 1999 WITH RESPECT TO INSURANCE COMPANIES

FDI related compliance with respect to ownership in Indian insurance companies are conferred in clause (aaa) of section 114(2) and clause (b) of section 2(7A) of Insurance Act, 1938 and section 24 of IRDA Act, 1999. In addition to this, the Central Government has also notified the Indian Insurance Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015 which mainly administer Indian control over Indian Insurance Company. This control includes Indian ownership and the various issues relating to foreign investment in private insurance sector. According to this rule, control in Indian ownership includes the following:

- Shareholding in Indian Private Sector Companies.
- Management rights in Indian Private Sector Companies.
- Shareholders agreements in Indian Private Sector Companies.
- Voting agreements in Indian Private Sector Companies.
- Any other manner as per applicable laws.

The applicability of these rules is covered in all types of insurance companies and companies involved in insurance activities in the following:

- All the insurance companies may come into existence after introduction of notification under these Acts.

- All the insurance companies may recommend to hike their foreign equity investment from the existing level, and
- All the insurance companies who do not have intention to enhance their current foreign capital stake from the existing level.

4.8 INDIAN OWNED AND CONTROLLED GUIDILINES WITH RESPECT TO FDI: AN OVERVIEW

The guidelines of “Indian Owned and controlled” are stated in Indian Insurance Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015. All type of insurance companies in India shall confirm the followings in respect to FDI management:

- Majority of the directors excluding independent directors should be appointed through direct nomination by the Indian investor.
- Appointment of all Key Management Persons (KMP) should be appointed through the Board of Directors by the Indian investor. KMP includes Chief Executive Officer (CEO), Managing Director (MD) and Principal Office (PO).
- Any KMP excluding CEO could be nominated by the foreign investor provided that such appointment of KMP is approved by the Board of Directors where the majority of the directors excluding independent directors are the nominees of Indian investor.
- All the issues regarding control over significant managerial policies of the insurance company should be exercised by the Board of Directors provided the majority of the directors excluding independent directors are the nominees of Indian investor.
- In case of voting, the Chairman of the Board of Directors having a right of casting vote. In this case, the Chairman should be nominated by the Indian investor.
- For all the meetings, quorum means and includes presence of majority of the Indian directors irrespective of whether a foreign investor’s nominee is present or not.
- The right of a nominee of Foreign Investor’s to constitute a valid quorum for meetings with a protective right and to that extent would not amount to control within the meaning.
- A certified copy of resolution passed by the Board of Directors confirming the compliance of “Indian owned and controlled” as stated in Indian Insurance

Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015 and should be submitted to the IRDA.

- A certified copy of the joint venture agreement should be prepared in accordance with “Indian owned and controlled” as stated in Indian Insurance Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015 and should be submitted to the IRDA.
- The Intermediaries of insurance companies as defined in the IRDA Act, 1999 such as Brokers, Third Party Administrators, Surveyors and Loss Assessors etc. having more than 50% of its revenue from the insurance activities shall have to follow rules of Indian Insurance Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015 if foreign investment is invited.
- All the existing Indian insurance companies are required to comply with the guidelines “Indian Owned and controlled” within a period of three months from the date of issue of these guidelines. In case of existing insurer, an application made with valid reasons may grant a further period of three months provided that the total time taken by an existing insurer to comply with “Indian owned and controlled” stipulations does not extend beyond six months.
- All the insurance companies coming into existence in the post issuance (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015 guidelines shall be taken a criteria grant of certificate of registration under IRDA Act, 1999.

CHAPTER- 5

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURERS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Chapter Outline:

5.1 Financial Performance in terms of Investment Behaviour, Investment Income and Annualized Investment Yield of Life Insurers (Aggregative) and Non-Life Insurers (Aggregative)

5.2 Comparison of the Average Performance with Respect to Investment Income and Annualized Yield between Life Insurers (Aggregative) and Non-Life Insurers (Aggregative)

5.3 Financial Performance in terms of Earnings and Financial Health Indicators of Life Insurers (Aggregative) and Non-Life Insurers (Aggregative)

5.4 Comparison of Average Performance with respect to Earnings and Financial Health Indicators between Life Insurers (Aggregative) and Non-Life Insurers (Aggregative)

5.5 Assessment of Difference in the Earnings and Financial Health Indicators due to Capital Structural Change of the Life and Non-Life Insurers during the Pre FDI hiked and Post FDI hiked Periods

5.6 Assessment of overall difference in the relationships between Earnings Indicators and FDI Inflows due to Capital Structural Change of the Life and Non-Life Insurers during the Pre FDI hiked and Post FDI hiked Periods

5.7 Financial Performance in terms of Revenue Linked Service Indicators of Life Insurers (Aggregative) and Non- Life Insurers (Aggregative)

Chapter – 5 Financial Performances of Private Life and Non-Life Insurers: A Comparative Analysis

In this chapter, comparative financial performance based on selected parameters between private life insurers and private non-life insurers have been analyzed at aggregate level.

The nature and scope of two types of insurance sectors are different. However, as far the operational aspect of a company in terms of ownership is concerned; the two insurance sectors can be compared in terms of their financial performance.

To conduct the analysis of financial performance between private life insurers and private non-life insurers, it is categorized in two broad aspects as follows:

- Financial performance in terms of investment behaviour, investment income and Annualized Investment Yield (AIY)).
- Financial performance in terms of earnings and financial health indicators. The selected indicators under this category are stated as follows:
 - Earnings Indicators: Return on Equity (ROE), Commission Expenses Ratio (CER) and Operating Expenses Ratio (OER).
 - Financial Health Indicators: Solvency Ratio (SR) and FDI Inflow Ratio (FDIR).
- Financial performance in terms revenue linked service indicators. The selected indicators under this category are stated as follows:
 - Number of New Policies Issued.
 - Number of New Grievances reported, and
 - Grievances Resolved Ratio (GRR).

5.1 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN TERMS OF INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR, INVESTMENT INCOME AND ANNUALIZED INVESTMENT YIELD OF LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE) AND NON LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE)

According to the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (Investment) Regulations, 2000 as on 14th August, 2000, every private life and non-life insurer is required to follow the ceiling of investments (shown in Table 1.2 and 1.2) from their available funds of investment. This ceiling is different for the private life insurers and the private non-life insurers. In bracket of this ceiling, it is the art of life insurers and

non-life insurers to make investment in such a way that the outcome of the investment will be effective which ultimately affects the investment income and annualized investment yield. Table 5.1 to 5.3 depicts the trend growth rates of the investment behavior, investment income and annualized investment yield of the private life and non-life insurers during the period of study.

Table 5.1: Trend Growth Rates of Investment Instruments as Financial Performance Indicator of Life Insurers

Instruments	R ²	Constant (a)	Growth Rate (%)	F Value	Comments
Central Government Securities	0.997	5.880 (1689.92)	6.0 ^{***} (49.34)	2435.18	Positive and Significant
State Government Securities	0.986	5.652 (544.64)	8.7 ^{***} (24.01)	576.65	Positive and Significant
Housing & Infrastructure	0.967	5.223 (501.67)	5.5 ^{***} (15.28)	233.63	Positive and Significant
Approved Investments	0.919	5.718 (515.56)	3.7 ^{***} (9.5)	90.25	Positive and Significant
Other Investments	0.511	4.731 (81.14)	5.9 ^{**} (0.646)	8.36	Positive and Significant
Total Investment	0.997	6.295 (1878.33)	5.9 ^{***} (50.860)	2586.71	Positive and Significant

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. The trend co-efficient (represented by 'b') has been multiplied by 100 to express the growth rate in percentage form.
- ii. *** marked values indicatesignificant (acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed)
- iii. ** marked value indicates significant (acceptance) at 5% level (Two-tailed)
- iv. Figures in bracket indicate't' value
- v. d.f. = (n-k-1)> (10-1-1) =8

From Table 5.1, it is observed that the growth rate of all the financial instruments as per the ceiling of investment stated in Table 1.1 are positive and significant at 1% probability level which leads to the rejection of the first null hypothesis. It indicates that the investment behavior in terms of their growth in quantum is satisfactory for all the investment instruments. Growth in Central Government securities is highest (i.e., 49.34%) followed by 2nd highest growth in State Government securities (i.e., 24.01%) which shows that investment behavior by the life insurers are Government centric that ultimately is favorable for the Government to generate more funds available for Government expenditure. The growth rates of other instruments like housing, infrastructure and approved investments (i.e., Financial Market) are also satisfactory.

Table 5.2: Trend Growth Rates of Investment Instruments as Financial Performance Indicator of Non-Life Insurers

Instruments	R ²	Constant (a)	Growth Rate (%)	F Value	Comments
Central Government Securities	0.995	4.652 (882.74)	7.4 ^{***} (40.19)	1615.45	Positive and Significant
State Government Securities	0.991	4.323 (466.39)	9.8 ^{***} (30.42)	925.38	Positive and Significant
Housing funds and Loans to State Government for Housing along with Fire Fighting equipment	0.987	4.217 (456.26)	8.0 ^{***} (25.01)	625.57	Positive and Significant
Infrastructure Investments	0.985	4.453 (487.63)	7.2 ^{***} (22.65)	513.26	Positive and Significant
Approved Investments	0.989	4.765 (820.30)	5.5 ^{**} (27.10)	734.77	Positive and Significant
Other Investments	0.804	3.80 (108.43)	7.0 ^{**} (5.734)	32.87	Positive and Significant
Total Investment	0.969	3.676 (222.62)	9.1 ^{***} (15.91)	253.23	Positive and Significant

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. The trend co-efficient (represented by 'b') has been multiplied by 100 to express the growth rate in percentage form.
- ii. *** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed)
- iii. ** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 5% level (Two-tailed)
- iv. Figures in bracket indicate 't' value
- v. d.f. = (n-k-1) > (10-1-1) = 8

Table 5.2 shows that the growth rates of all the investment instruments are positive and statistically significant at 1% acceptance level during the study period by the non-life insurers which leads to the rejection of the first null hypothesis. It depicts the favorable investment behaviors in terms of the ceiling of investment shown in Table 1.2 by the non-life insurers. Investment growth in Central Government securities is higher i.e., 40.19% among all the investment instruments. Growth rate of investment in Statement Government securities, Housing funds and Loans to State Government for Housing along with Fire Fighting equipment, Infrastructure Investments and Approved Investments ranges from 22% to 31%. This shows a balance growth in all investment instruments by the non- life insurers.

Table 5.3: Trend Growth Rates of Investment Income as Financial Performance Indicator of Life and Non-Life Insurers

Statistical Results	Investment Income		Annualized Investment Yield	
	Life Insurers	Non-life Insurers	Life Insurers	Non-life Insurers
R ²	0.0001	0.969	0.142	0.631
Constant (a)	4.425 (28.18)	3.676 (222.62)	-1.870 (-12.049)	-1.571 (-97.17)
Growth Rate (%)	-0.30 ⁱ (-0.053)	9.1 ^{***} (15.91)	-6.2 ⁱ (-1.151)	2.1 ^{***} (3.696)
F Value	0.003	253.23	1.326	13.65
Comments	Negative and Insignificant	Positive and Significant	Negative and Insignificant	Positive and Significant

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. The trend co-efficient (represented by 'b') has been multiplied by 100 to express the growth rate in percentage form.
- ii. *** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed)
- iii. *i* marked value indicates insignificant (non-acceptance)
- iv. Figures in bracket indicate 't' value
- v. d.f. = (n-k-1) > (10-1-1) = 8

Table 5.3 shows that growth rate of investment income and annualized investment yield by the life insurers are negative, although insignificant (acceptance of the first null hypothesis). It indicates that the performance of the investment instruments by the life insurers is not satisfactory during study period inspite of positive and significant growth (Shown in Table 5.1) of investment instruments during the study period. The life- insurers should need special attention on the investment in different instruments to generate satisfactory yield on investment.

On the other hand, Table 5.3 shows that the growth rate of investment income and annualized investment yield by the non-life insurers are positive and statistically significant at 1 % level of significance (rejection of the first null hypothesis) during the study period. It clearly indicates that the performance of the investment instruments of non-life insurer is favorable in connection with their growth in investment value which is positive and significant (Shown in Table 5.2) during the study period. It depicts that the investment management of the non-life insurers are satisfactory during the study period.

Table 5.3 also shows a comparative picture of investment performance of the life and non life insurers. In this respect, the performance of the non-life insurers are better than that of the life insurers in terms growth rate in investment income and annualized

investment yield, although both life and non-life insurers have positive and significant growth in investment during the study period.

5.2 COMPARISON OF THE AVERAGE PERFORMANCE WITH RESPECT TO INVESTMENT INCOME AND ANNUALIZED YIELD BETWEEN LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE) AND NON-LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE)

The word comparison means the process of considering how things, entities, or aspects are similar and how they are different from each other.

Fisher’s “t” test is generally used to test for equality of two means when population standard deviation is unknown and the sample size is small (i.e., less than 30). Basically, t-test is a method of inferential statistic which is applied to measure if there is any significant difference between the means of two groups, which may be associated in certain features.

This comparison helps to establish how likely the difference between the means occurred by chance or whether the data series really have basic difference(s). The t-test enquires whether the difference between the groups represents a factual difference of the study or not.

To find out the difference of means of performance indicators like investment income and annualized investment yield between life insurers (aggregate) and non-life insurers (aggregate), we employed “t” test.

Table 5.4: Results of t-test for difference of mean with respect to Investment Income and Annualized Yield between Life Insurers (Aggregate) and Non-Life (Aggregate)

Indicators	t-Value	Level of Significance	Results
Investment Income	4.119 ^{***}	1%	Significant, H ₀ Rejected
Annualized Investment Yield	-1.62 ⁱ	5%	Insignificant, H ₀ Accepted

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. *** marked value indicates significant(acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed)
- ii. *i* marked value indicates insignificant(non-acceptance)
- iii. d.f. = (n₁+ n₂-2) = (10+10-2) =18

From Table 5.4, it is observed that the difference between the performances of the private life and non- life insurers in terms of investment income is significant at 1%

probability level. This implies that the investment income performance in aggregate is significantly different between private life and non-life insurers and it also leads to the rejection of the 2nd hypothesis (H_{O2} :*There is no significant difference in average financial performance with respect to selected performance parameters between private Life and Non-Life Insurers*). This points out to the fact that life and non-life insurers have significant differences in managing their investment instruments to generate investment income, although the growth of investment are positive in both the insurers during the study period.

On the other hand, in terms of annualized investment yield, the difference between the performance of private life and non-life insurers is insignificant which implies that there is no difference in the average performance and it also leads to the acceptance of the 2nd hypothesis (H_{O2} :*There is no significant difference in average financial performance with respect to selected performance parameters between private Life and Non-Life Insurers*). The growth of the annualized yield by the non-life insurers is positive in comparison to the life insurers. However, the average performance of the non-life insurers is almost similar to the life insurers. So, both the insurers should concentrate on the management of the investment instruments to generate higher annualized investment yield that affects the earnings of the insurers.

5.3 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN TERMS OF EARNINGS AND FINANCIAL HEALTH INDICATORS OF LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE) AND NON LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE)

As discussed in the beginning of this chapter, financial performance is to be measured in two broad aspects: firstly on earnings indicators and secondly on financial health indicators. The selected financial indicators are ROE, CER, and OR. All these indicators are directly related with total earnings of the private life and non-life insurers. Higher growth of ROE is favorable and lower growth of OR is favorable. CER is directly related with business growth of the insurances as the growth in new policies issued dependson the agent's performances and the same also effects the commission. So, growth in CER also indicates the growth of earnings of the life and non-life insurers.

On the other hand, financial health indicators are SR and FDIR which indicates the solvency i.e.,debt equity composition and the FDI contribution in the total equity of the life and non-life insurers. In accordance with the restriction of the maximum FDI

investment ceiling (from the year 2015, the Government of India hiked the FDI capital in private life and non-life insurers from 26 per cent to 49 per cent), higher growth in FDI indicates effective external equity management of the private life and non-life insurers. As the FDI inflows are directly related with the external equity management, it directly affects earning indicators and financial health indicators of life and non-life insurers. Table 5.5 and 5.6 depicts the trend growth rates of the earning and financial health indicators during the study period.

Table 5.5: Trend Growth Rates of Earnings and Financial Health Indicators of Life Insurers

Instruments	R ²	Constant (a)	Growth Rate (%)	F Value	Comments
Return on Equity(ROE)	0.216	-0.739 (-14.90)	2.6 ⁱ (1.48)	2.21	Positive and Insignificant
Commission Expenses Ratio(CER)	0.001	-1.280 (-85.01)	-0.1 ⁱ (-0.09)	0.009	Negative and Insignificant
Operating Expenses Ratio(OER)	0.834	-0.801 (-88.28)	-2.0 ^{***} (-6.34)	40.27	Negative and Significant
Solvency Ratio(SR)	0.703	0.523 (61.876)	-1.3 ^{***} (-4.35)	18.95	Negative and Significant
FDI Inflow Ratio(FDIR)	0.787	-0.543 (-40.97)	2.5 ^{***} (5.434)	29.52	Positive and Significant

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. The trend co-efficient (represented by 'b') has been multiplied by 100 to express the growth rate in percentage form.
- ii. *** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed)
- iii. ⁱmarked values indicate insignificant (non-acceptance)
- iv. Figures in bracket indicate 't' value
- v. d.f. = (n-k-1) > (10-1-1) = 8

Table 5.5 shows positive growth rate in ROE and FDIR. However, the result is significant for FDIR and insignificant for ROE. Furthermore, OER and SR show significant negative growth, while CER reveals insignificant negative growth. These results lead to the acceptance of the first hypothesis for ROE and CER, while the same hypothesis is rejected for OER, SR, and FDIR. Since the growth rate in ROE is positive and insignificant, earnings by the investors can be regarded as satisfactory that comprises of equity capital from Indian investors and FDI investors. The CER growth is negative although insignificant. This indicates that cost to the insurance companies has not increased due to high agent's commission as compared to the gross premium collected which ultimately reduces the outflow of the insurers. Thus, it

consequently increases the additions for the policy holders and returns of the insurers. Negative and significant growth of OER reveals effective management of the administrative expenses by the private life insurers.

In the context of financial health indicators, higher level of solvency ratio indicates better financial health. However, in the study, the growth rate is negative and significant which indicates that solvency position has not improved. Since the Government increases the ceiling of the FDI inflows, a positive and significant growth in FDIR as observed during the study period indicates an increase in the composition of FDI equity capital in the capital structure of the life insurers. Thus, considering the growth of all parameters, increase in FDI has not brought desired results with respect to all the earnings and financial health indicators of private life insurers during the study period.

Table 5.6: Trend Growth Rates of Earnings and Financial Health Indicators of Non-Life Insurers

Instruments	R ²	Constant (a)	Growth Rate (%)	F Value	Comments
Return on Equity(ROE)	0.383	-0.698 (-16.11)	3.4 ^t (1.48)	4.96	Positive and Insignificant
Commission Expenses Ratio(CER)	0.537	-1.073 (-99.14)	1.1 ^{**} (3.04)	9.28	Positive and Significant
Operating Expenses Ratio(OER)	0.004	-0.675 (-59.823)	-0.1 ^t (-0.172)	0.02	Negative and Insignificant
Solvency Ratio(SR)	0.377	0.348 (26.99)	-1.0 ^t (-2.19)	4.83	Negative and Insignificant
FDI Inflow Ratio(FDIR)	0.692	-0.601 (-33.62)	2.6 ^{***} (4.23)	17.96	Positive and Significant

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. The trend co-efficient (represented by 'b') has been multiplied by 100 to express the growth rate in percentage form.
- ii. *** marked value indicates significant (acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed)
- iii. ** marked value indicates significant (acceptance) at 5% level (Two-tailed)
- iv. *i* marked values indicate insignificant (non-acceptance)
- v. Figures in bracket indicate 't' value
- vi. d.f. = (n-k-1) > (10-1-1) = 8

Table 5.6 reveals affirmative growth rate in ROE, CER, and FDIR, although the result is significant for CER and FDIR, leading to the rejection of the first null hypothesis of the study. Moreover, OER and SR show insignificant negative growth and these results lead to the acceptance of the first null hypothesis of the study. The ROE growth rate is positive, although it is insignificant. Therefore, it indicates that earnings

of the owners have not improved due to inclusion of FDI inflows in the equity composition. Since the growth of the CER is positive and significant, it indicates that the cost to the insurers has increased consequently, thereby reduces the return to the policy holders of non-life insurers as well as returns to the insurer. Negative growth of OER is desirable but it is insignificant which reveals the management of the administrative expenses is not satisfactory by the private life insurers. So FDI inflow in the equity composition is not effective towards the management of OER.

With respect to financial health indicator, higher level of solvency ratio indicates better financial health. However, the study result shows negative growth (although insignificant) which indicates that solvency position is static. Since the Government increases the ceiling of the FDI inflows, a positive and significant growth rate in FDIR during the study period shows an increase in the composition of FDI equity capital in the capital structure of the non-life insurers.

Considering the growth rates of all the parameters, the above results indicate that noteworthy increase in FDI has not brought desirable results of all the earnings and financial health indicators of the private non-life insurers during the study time.

5.4 COMPARISON OF AVERAGE PERFORMANCE WITH RESPECT TO EARNINGS AND FINANCIAL HEALTH INDICATORS BETWEEN LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE) AND NON-LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE)

To find out the difference of means of earnings indicators (i.e. ROE, CER, and OR) and financial health indicators (i.e. SR and FDIR) between life insurers (aggregate) and non-life insurers (aggregate), we employed “t” test.

The results showed in Table 5.7.

Table 5.7: Results of t-test for difference of mean with respect to Earnings and Financial Health Indicators between Life Insurers (Aggregative) and Non-Life (Aggregative)

Indicators	t-Value	Level of Significance	Results
Return on Equity(ROE)	0.859 ⁱ	5%	Insignificant, H ₀₂ Accepted
Commission Expenses Ratio(CER)	9.9 ^{***}	1%	Significant, H ₀₂ Rejected
Operating Expenses Ratio(OER)	-5.34 ^{***}	1%	Significant, H ₀₂ Rejected
Solvency Ratio(SR)	7.57 ^{***}	1%	Significant, H ₀₂ Rejected
FDI Inflow Ratio(FDIR)	1.75 ⁱ	5%	Insignificant, H ₀₂ Accepted

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. *** marked values indicatesignificant (acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed)
- ii. *i* marked values indicate insignificant(non- acceptance)
- iii. d.f. = (n₁+ n₂-2) = (10+10-2) =18

From Table 5.7, it is observed that the difference between the performances of the private life and non- life insurers in terms of earnings indicator ROE and financial health indicator FDIR are insignificant. This implies thatROE and FDIR performance in aggregate is not different between private life and non-life insurers and it also leads to the acceptance of the 2nd hypothesis (*H₀₂:There is no significant difference in average financial performance with respect to selected performance parameters between private Life and Non-Life Insurers*).This plugs out to the point that the life and non-life insurers haveno differences in equity earnings and FDI inflows in their capital structure. This shows similar equity capital management by both the insurers during the study period.

It is also observed in Table 5.7 that the difference between the performance of the private life and non- life insurers in terms of earnings indicator (i.e., CER and OR) and financial health indicator (SR) are significant at 1% probability level. This infers that CER, OR, and SR performances in aggregate are different between private life and non-life insurers and it also indicates to the rejection of the 2nd hypothesis (*H₀₂:There is no significant difference in average financial performance with respect to selected performance parameters between private Life and Non-Life Insurers*).This plugs out to the argument that the life and non-life insurers have differences in commission expenses management towards their agents and operating expenses

management to run administration during the study period. So far external equity management is concerned in terms of SR, it shows difference in that between the life and non- life insurers, although both have negative and insignificant growth during the study period.

5.5 ASSESSMENT OF DIFFERENCE IN THE EARNINGS AND FINANCIAL HEALTH INDICATORS DUE TO CAPITAL STRUCTURAL CHANGE OF THE LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURERS DURING THE PRE FDI HIKED AND POST FDI HIKED PERIODS

In India, the IRDA Act, 1999 liberalized the inflow of foreign shareholdings commonly known as FDI for the private life and non-life insurance companies from 26 per cent to 49 per cent of the total shareholding with effect from the year 2015. The change in equity composition leads to huge changes in the capital structure which leads to changes in the management and its operating style. So, it can be regarded as a structural change which has direct effect on the earnings and financial health indicators of the private life and non-life insurers during the pre and post FDI hiked periods.

Chow test is used to measure the differences in financial growth of the private life and non-life insurers in India during the study period. The results are shown in Table 5.8 and 5.9 respectively.

Table 5.8: Chow Test for Examining the Differences in Growth Rates of Performance Indicators between Two Sub Periodswith respect to Life Insurers

Selected Performance Indicators	Calculated Value of F-Statistic	Differences in Growth Rates between Two Sub-Periods	
Return on Equity(ROE)	3.156	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}
Commission Expenses Ratio(CER)	12.00	Significant at 1% Level	Reject H_{03}
Operating Expenses Ratio(OER)	2.27	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}
Solvency Ratio(SR)	5.57	Significant at 5% Level	Reject H_{03}
FDI Inflow Ratio(FDIR)	10.68	Significant at 5% Level	Reject H_{03}

Source: Computed

Table 5.8 reveals insignificant results for ROE and OER, which indicates that there has been no significant change due to the hike of ceiling in FDI during the study period. These results lead to the acceptance of the third hypothesis (H_{03} : *There is no*

significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study) for ROE and OER. However, the results are found to be significant for CER, SR and FDIR which means that there is a significant change in these parameters due to the hike of ceiling in FDI. So, for CER, SR, and FDIR, the third hypothesis (H_{03} : There is no significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurance companies due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study) has been rejected in the study.

From the above results, no definite conclusion can be arrived as it shows different results with respect to selected earnings and financial health performance parameters.

Table 5.9: Chow Test for Examining the Differences in Growth Rates of Performance Indicators between Two Sub Periods with respect to Non-Life Insurers

Selected Performance Indicators	Calculated Value of F-Statistic	Differences in Growth Rates between Two Sub-Periods	
Return on Equity(ROE)	2.65	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}
Commission Expenses Ratio(CER)	6.00	Significant at 5% Level	Reject H_{03}
Operating Expenses Ratio(OER)	0.030	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}
Solvency Ratio(SR)	1.33	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}
FDI Inflow Ratio(FDIR)	1.34	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}

Source: Computed

Table 5.9 shows unimportant results for ROE, OER, SR, and FDIR which means there has been no significant change in these parameters due to hike of ceiling in FDI during the study period. This leads to the acceptance of the third null hypothesis (H_{03} : There is no significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study) for ROE, OER, SR, and FDIR. However, significant result is observed for CER, which indicates that there is important change in the growth rates of CER. This also leads to the rejection of the third null hypothesis (H_{03} : There is no significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study) of the study.

From the above results, no definite decision can be arrived since it shows different results with respect to selected earnings performance parameters.

5.6 ASSESSMENT OF OVERALL DIFFERENCE IN THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN EARNINGS INDICATORS AND FDI INFLOWS DUE TO CAPITAL STRUCTURAL CHANGE OF THE LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURERS DURING THE PRE FDI HIKED AND POST FDI HIKED PERIODS

From the results shown in 5.8 and 5.9, it is difficult to arrive any core conclusion as different opinions are obtained in respect of earnings and financial health parameters of the life insurers and earnings parameters of the non-life insurers due to hike in the ceiling of FDI during the period of study.

If we consider the selected earnings parameters, ROE can be regarded as the prime indicator as it shows return for the equity holder which is a better measure of profitability. ROE is directly related with CER and OER since ROE is measured after consideration of commission expenses and operating expenses. ROE is also related with the financial health indicator (FDIR) since it comprises changes in the owners fund and administrative aspect of the management. This also affects commission expenses and operating expenses.

On the other hand, financial health indicator (SR) is dependent on FDIR as it affects the changes in equity and debt composition.

Therefore, to arrive at a definite conclusion, we run two regression equations and the estimated beta coefficients of the respective equations are applied in the Chow test. The first equation takes ROE as dependent variable and the independent variables are represented by CER, OER, and FDIR. In the second regression equation, the dependent variable is represented by SR and the independent variable is represented by FDIR.

Table 5.10 and 5.11 shows the result of Chow Test as per the above stated criteria.

Table 5.10: Chow Test for Examining the Overall Differences in Growth Rate of Earning Indicators of Life Insurers between the Two Sub Periods

Selected Performance Indicators	Calculated Value of F-Statistic	Differences in Growth Rates between Two Sub-Periods	
ROE- Life Insurers	0.500	Insignificant at 5% Level	AcceptH ₀₃
SR- Life Insurers	3.686	Insignificant at 5% Level	AcceptH ₀₃

Source: Computed

From table 5.10, it is found that Chow F Statistic value of ROE and SR of private life insurers is insignificant at 5% probability level, which leads to the acceptance of third null hypothesis (H_{03} : *There is no significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study*) of the study. This shows that there has been no change in growth rates of earnings and financial health indicators due to hike in FDI ceiling during the period under study.

Table 5.11: Chow Test for Examining the Overall Differences in Growth Rate of Financial Health Indicators of Non- Life Insurers between the Two Sub Periods

Selected Performance Indicators	Calculated Value of F-Statistic	Differences in Growth Rates between Two Sub-Periods	
ROE- Non-Life Insurers	0.281	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}
SR- Non-Life Insurers	1.478	Insignificant at 5% Level	Accept H_{03}

Source: Computed

Table 5.11 shows insignificant results for both ROE and SR of private non-life insurers in India. This also leads to the acceptance of the third premise (H_{03} : *There is no significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study*) of the study. Thus, it indicates that there has been no alteration in growth rates of the selected fiscal performance indicators due to hike in FDI ceiling during the study period.

5.7 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN TERMS OF REVENUE LINKED SERVICE INDICATORS OF LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE) AND NON LIFE INSURERS (AGGREGATIVE)

Financial performance of earnings and financial health indicators are also indirectly associated with some revenue linked service indicator. The key indicators in this respect are i. Number of New Policies Issued, ii. Number of New Grievances Reported and iii. Grievances Resolved Ratio (GRR). The increase in new policies is indicative to the increase in revenues and insurance penetration. If the service qualities of the insurers are adequate then new grievances reported will be minimum which ultimately affects the increase of new policies issued. GRR indicates the performance of resolving the grievances if any. The revenue linked service indicators

are also associated with the management of the insurers which is dependent on the FDI inflows as it changes the ownership. Table 5.12 and 5.13 shows the results of growth of service indicator number of policies issued and number of new grievances reported by the life and non-life insurers.

Table 5.12: Trend Growth Rates of Revenue Linked Service Indicators of Life Insurers

Instruments	R ²	Constant (a)	Growth Rate (%)	F Value	Comments
Number of New Policies Issued	0.297	1.854 (79.89)	-1.5 ⁱ (1.48)	3.35	Negative and Insignificant
Number of New Grievances Reported	0.001	4.995 (30.60)	-1.5 ⁱ (-0.09)	0.008	Negative and Insignificant

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. The trend co-efficient (represented by 'b') has been multiplied by 100 to express the growth rate in percentage form.
- ii. *i*marked values indicate insignificant(non-acceptance).
- iii. Figures in bracket indicate't' value.
- iv. d.f. = (n-k-1) > (10-1-1) =8

Table 5.12 indicates that there is an insignificant growth in respect of new policies issued which shows that the coverage of insurance penetration by the life insurer is not satisfactory during the study period. As the growth rate of incremental new policies is negative, it will affect the revenue indicators of the life insurers. On the other hand, the growth rate of new grievances reported in respect to the services is negative but insignificant. This clearly indicates that the quality of services provided by the life insurersto some extent is satisfactory during the study period.

Table 5.13: Trend Growth Rates of Revenue Linked Service Indicators of Non-Life Insurers

Instruments	R ²	Constant (a)	Growth Rate (%)	F Value	Comments
Number of New Policies Issued	0.980	12.759 (254.12)	7.4 ^{***} (19.63)	385.49	Positive and Significant
Number of New Grievances Reported	0.014	4.462 (31.85)	1.7 ⁱ (0.34)	0.11	Positive and Insignificant

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. The trend co-efficient (represented by 'b') has been multiplied by 100 to express the growth rate in percentage form.
- ii. *** marked value indicates significant (acceptance) at 1% level (Two-tailed).
- iii. *i*marked value indicates insignificant(non-acceptance).
- iv. Figures in bracket indicate't' value.
- v. d.f. = (n-k-1) > (10-1-1) =8

Table 5.13 shows that the number of policies newly issued by the non life insurers is positive and significant at 1% acceptance level. It indicates that the coverage of insurance penetration by the non-life insurers is satisfactory during the study period. It will affect the revenue indicators of the non-life insurers. The growth rate of new grievances reported in respect of policies issued is found to be positive but insignificant, which indicates that the quality of services provided by the non- life insurers are satisfactory to some extent.

Table 5.14 shows the average GRR of the life and non-life insurers.

GRR is computed on the basis of the following formula:

$$\text{Grievances Resolved Ratio (GRR)} = \frac{\text{Grievances Resolved}}{\text{Grievances outstanding at the beginning of the year} + \text{New grievances reported during the year}}$$

Higher GRR is acceptable and it also shows the service quality of the life and non-life insurers.

Table 5.14: Grievances Resolved Ratio of Life and Non-Life Insurers

Year	Grievances Resolved Ratio(in Percentage)	
	Life Insurers	Non-Life Insurers
2010-11	97.43	89.91
2011-12	99.49	99.62
2012-13	99.74	99.79
2013-14	99.59	99.67
2014-15	96.93	96.31
2015-16	99.36	98.96
2016-17	99.73	99.20
2017-18	99.74	98.41
2018-19	99.86	101.62
2019-20	99.95	99.89
Average	99.18	98.34
Standard Deviation	1.08	3.25

Source: Computed

Table 5.14 shows that the average grievances resolved ratios by the both life and non-life insurers are satisfactory as it is over 98%. But if we compare the situation, then we find that the performance of grievance resolved ratios by the life insurers are slightly better than that of the non- life insurers with lower standard deviation. Table 5.14 also reveals that there are some inconsistencies in the grievances resolved by the

non-life insurers i.e., 89.91% in 2010-11 and 96.31% in 2014-15 which generates higher standard deviation of the non-life insurers during the study period. So, the non-life insurers should concentrate on this matter to achieve more in terms of average grievances resolved ratio.

The new number of grievances reported in absolute terms shows the service quality of the life and non life insurers and the same can be influenced by the FDI inflows since it relates with the equity composition that affects the management and its activities. The changes in the ceiling of FDI from 26% to 49% w.e.f. 2015 may have tendency of changes in the operating activities of the private insurers. Table 5.15 and Chart 1 show the effect of the same during the period of the study.

Table 5.15: Number of New Grievances Reported of Life and Non-Life Insurers

Year	Grievances Reported (in Numbers)	
	Life Insurers	Non-Life Insurers
2010-11	7068	2430
2011-12	257313	80497
2012-13	267978	60311
2013-14	289336	45677
2014-15	198048	44828
2015-16	139951	41277
2016-17	90063	33051
2017-18	77183	21427
2018-19	61137	21793
2019-20	53212	26986

Source: Computed

Figure 5.1: Number of New Grievances Reported of Life and Non-Life Insurers

Source: Computed

Table 5.15 and Figure 5.1 shows that there are few number of grievances reported in the year 2010-11 for the life insurers and it has drastically increased from the year 2011-12 to 2013-14. A highlighting declining trend is observed from the year 2014-15 to 2019-20. So, the changes in the ceiling of FDI inflows from 2014-15 may have an effect in the service quality of the life insurers. The minimum number of grievances reported can be treated as outcome of better service quality by the life insurers. The changes in the management due to FDI inflows can be said as an indicator of this better outcome.

On the other hand, Table 5.15 and Chart 1 shows that the new grievances reported for the non-life insurers has drastically increased from the year 2010-11 to the year 2011-12 and then gradually decreases from 2012-13 to 2017-18. In the year 2018-19, it has slightly increased and in the year 2019-20 it has increased to a considerable amount. The trend for the decline in the new grievances reported for the non-life insurers shown before the changes in the ceiling of FDI i.e. from the year 2014-15 but from the year 2018-19 an increasing trend also observed. So, the changes in the ceiling of FDI inflows and changes in the management thereof can't have positive impact on the service quality of the non-life insurers. A mixed observation is located in the declining trend of new grievances reported by the non-life insurers during the period of study.

CHAPTER- 6

FDI IN INSURANCE SECTOR: IMPACT ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURERS

Chapter Outline:

- 6.1 Model 1: Multivariate Regression Analysis (MVRA) of Life Insurers with FDI Inflows*
- 6.2 Model 2: Multivariate Regression Analysis (MVRA) of Life Insurers without FDI Inflows*
- 6.3 Model 1: Multivariate Regression Analysis (MVRA) of Non-Life Insurers with FDI Inflows*
- 6.4 Model 2: Multivariate Regression Analysis (MVRA) of Non-Life Insurers Without FDI Inflows*

Chapter – 6 FDI in Insurance Sector: Impact on Financial Performance of Private Life and Non-Life Insurers

In this chapter, impact of FDI inflows on the financial performance parameters of the private Life and Non-Life insurers have been analyzed at aggregate level.

The earnings indicator ROE (the best measure of profitability) and financial health indicator SR (the best measure of solvency of the insurers) actually shows the overall financial performance of the life and non-life insurers. So, ROE and SR can be regarded as prime financial indicator of the insurers in terms of profitability. The other earnings indicators (CER, OER, GRR, AIY and FDIR) also have impact on ROE and SR. Here, the effect of FDIR is to be noticed on these variables to analyze the impact of FDI inflows on ROE and SR. For that purpose, Multivariate Regression Analysis (MRVA) has been applied with two dependent variables (i.e., ROE and SR) and five independent variables (i.e., CER, OER, GRR, AIY and FDIR) as per data.

First, we consider the case for Life insurers, where two different models are developed as stated below.

Model 1: Run Multivariate Regression Analysis (MVRA) of life and non-life insurers at aggregate level with consideration of FDIR.

Model 2: Run Multivariate Regression Analysis (MRVA) of life and non-life insurers at aggregate level without consideration of FDIR.

6.1 MODEL 1: MULTIVARIATE REGRESSION ANALYSIS (MVRA) OF LIFE INSURERS WITH FDI INFLOWS

Table 6.1 shows the MVRA of two dependent variable ROE and SR with five independent variables CER, OER, GRR, AIY and FDIR.

Table: 6.1: Coefficients of MVRA of ROE and SR of Life Insurers

Response ROE				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-5.908	1.726	-3.423	0.0267**
CER	1.796	2.560	0.701	0.5217 ^t
OER	-4.872	1.992	-2.446	0.0708 ^t
FDIR	-2.282	0.927	-2.462	0.0696 ^t
GRR	7.452	2.058	3.622	0.0223**
AIY	3.045	1.295	2.352	0.0784 ^t
Residual standard error: 0.03247 on 4 degrees of freedom				
Multiple R-squared: 0.8015, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5533				
F-statistic: 3.23 on 5 and 4 DF, p-value: 0.1395				

Response SR				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.142	7.323	0.293	0.784 ⁱ
CER	-20.402	10.860	-1.879	0.133 ⁱ
OER	-1.769	8.451	-0.209	0.844 ⁱ
FDIR	-7.074	3.933	-1.799	0.146 ⁱ
GRR	4.815	8.728	0.552	0.611 ⁱ
AIY	-7.336	5.493	-1.336	0.253 ⁱ
Residual standard error: 0.1377 on 4 degrees of freedom				
Multiple R-squared: 0.9314, Adjusted R-squared: 0.8457				
F-statistic: 10.86 on 5 and 4 DF, p-value: 0.01919				

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. ** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 5% level
- ii. *i* marked values indicate insignificant(non-acceptance)

From Table 6.1, it is observed that in response to ROE, the co-efficient of the independent variables CER, OER, FDIR and AIY are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of 4th null hypothesis (H_{O4} : FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers) and only one independent variable GRR is significant which leads to the rejection of the 4th null hypothesis. Since all the independent variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on ROE for life insurers during the study period.

In response to SR, the co-efficient of all the independent variables CER, OER, FDIR, AIY and GRR are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of the 4th null hypothesis (H_{O4} : FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers). Since all the independent variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on SR for life insurers during the study period. Thus, in both the cases, FDI inflows does not put any significant impact on the prime earnings indicator (ROE) and prime financial health indicator (SR) of the life insurance companies.

Table 6.2 shows the variation of independent variables in the sample

**Table: 6.2: MANOVA Test of Model I of Life Insurers
(Pillai Test Statistic)**

	Df	Test statistic	approx F	num Df	den Df	Pr(>F)
CER	1	0.66006	2.9125	2	3	0.19820 ⁱ
OER	1	0.66046	2.9177	2	3	0.19785 ⁱ
FDIR	1	0.61377	2.3837	2	3	0.24003 ⁱ
GRR	1	0.80000	5.9999	2	3	0.08944 ⁱ
AIY	1	0.79253	5.7301	2	3	0.09450 ⁱ

Source: Computed

Note:

- i. *i* marked values indicate insignificant(non-acceptance)

Table 6.2 shows that test statistic of the entire variable are insignificant. So, no variations in the mean of all these variables are present in this sample. Now, no direct conclusion on the impact of FDI inflows on ROE and SR can be arrived. Hence, we apply Model 2, where the independent variable FDIR is excluded to judge whether FDI have any effect on the ROE and SR or not.

6.2 MODEL 2: MULTIVARIATE REGRESSION ANALYSIS (MVRA) OF LIFE INSURERS WITHOUT FDI INFLOWS

Table 6.3 shows the MVRA of two dependent variable ROE and SR with four independent variables CER, OER, GRR, and AIY (i.e., the exclusion of FDIR).

**Table: 6.3: Coefficients of MVRA of ROE and SR of Life Insurers
(without FDIR)**

Response ROE				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-3.2889	1.9279	-1.706	0.149 ⁱ
CER	-1.2441	3.1807	-0.391	0.712 ⁱ
OER	-0.1168	0.6891	-0.170	0.872 ⁱ
GRR	3.5517	1.8616	1.908	0.115 ⁱ
AIY	2.1925	1.7696	1.239	0.270 ⁱ
Residual standard error: 0.04606 on 5 degrees of freedom Multiple R-squared: 0.5007, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1013 F-statistic: 1.254 on 4 and 5 DF, p-value: 0.3966				

Response SR				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	10.262	6.936	1.479	0.19910 ⁱ
CER	-29.825	11.444	-2.606	0.04789 ^{**}
OER	12.973	2.479	5.232	0.00338 ^{**}
GRR	-7.276	6.698	-1.086	0.32690 ⁱ
AIY	-9.978	6.367	-1.567	0.17785 ⁱ
Residual standard error: 0.1657 on 5 degrees of freedom Multiple R-squared: 0.8759, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7766 F-statistic: 8.823 on 4 and 5 DF, p-value: 0.0173				

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. ** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 5% level
- ii. *i* marked values indicate insignificant (non-acceptance)

From Table 6.3, it is observed that in response to ROE, the co-efficient of all the independent variables are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of 4th null hypothesis (H_{04} : FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers). Since all the independent variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on ROE.

In response to SR, the co-efficient of the independent variables GRR and AIY are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of 4th null hypothesis (H_{04} : FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers). Co- efficient of CER and OER are significant at 5% probability level which leads to the rejection of the 4th null hypothesis. Since all the variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on SR. Thus, in both the cases, FDI inflow does not put any significant impact on the prime earnings indicator (ROE) and prime financial health indicator (SR) of the life insurance companies.

Figure 6.1 and 6.3 shows graphical representation of all the independent variables in response to ROE and SR with the inclusion of FDIR as independent variable and exclusion of FDIR as independent variable to show the effect of FDIR.

Figure 6.1: Coefficient Plot of Model-1 Life Insurers with FDIR

Source: Computed

Figure 6.1 show the shaded part of non-acceptance region where all the independent variable lies on that part. So, it can be concluded that FDIR have no special impact on ROE and SR. The variables perfectly lie within the confidence limit, i.e., none has any impact on the earnings indicator and financial health indicator of the life insurers i.e., they are not significantly different from weight of null hypothesis i.e., 0.

Figure 6.2: Coefficient Plot of Model-1 Life Insurers without FDIR

Figure 6.2 depicts the shaded part of non-acceptance region where all the independent variable lies except OER. Since all the variables are not outside on that part, it can be concluded that the FDIR have no special impact on ROE and SR. Thus, only OER is

significant when regression is run without FDI inflow variable. Other variables also appeared to be insignificant.

6.3 MODEL 1: MULTIVARIATE REGRESSION ANALYSIS (MVRA) OF NON- LIFE INSURERS WITH FDI INFLOWS

Table 6.4 shows the MVRA of two dependent variable ROE and SR with five independent variables CER, OER, GRR, AIY, and FDIR in respect of the non-life insurers.

Table: 6.4: Coefficients of MVRA of ROE and SR of Non-Life Insurers

Response ROE				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.1160	1.2105	-0.096	0.9283 ⁱ
CER	4.0164	3.6017	1.115	0.3273 ⁱ
OER	-2.7782	2.0465	-1.358	0.2462 ⁱ
FDIR	0.1963	0.6998	0.281	0.7929 ⁱ
GRR	-0.4765	1.0849	-0.439	0.6832 ⁱ
AIY	33.6810	8.8299	3.814	0.0189 ^{**}
Residual standard error: 0.07892 on 4 degrees of freedom Multiple R-squared: 0.9201, Adjusted R-squared: 0.8203 F-statistic: 9.216 on 5 and 4 DF, p-value: 0.02571				
Response SR				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	8.1857	2.8459	2.876	0.0452 ^{**}
CER	-5.6688	8.4680	-0.669	0.5399 ⁱ
OER	-3.6360	4.8115	-0.756	0.4919 ⁱ
FDIR	0.5513	1.6452	0.335	0.7544 ⁱ
GRR	-4.1152	2.5508	-1.613	0.1820 ⁱ
AIY	-28.7811	20.7599	-1.386	0.2379 ⁱ
Residual standard error: 0.1856 on 4 degrees of freedom Multiple R-squared: 0.7839, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5139 F-statistic: 2.903 on 5 and 4 DF, p-value: 0.162				

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. ** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 5% level
- i. ⁱ marked values indicate insignificant(non-acceptance)

From Table 6.4, it is observed that in response to ROE, the co-efficient of the independent variables CER, OER, FDIR, and GRR are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of 4th null hypothesis (H_{O4} : FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and

Non-Life Insurers) and only one independent variable AIY is significant which leads to the rejection of 4th null hypothesis. Since all the independent variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on ROE for non- life insurers during the study period.

In response to SR, the co-efficient of all the independent variables CER, OER, FDIR, AIY, and GRR are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of 4th null hypothesis(H_{04} : FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers). Since all the independent variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on SR for non-life insurers during the study period. Thus, in both the cases, FDI inflows do not put any significant impact on the prime earnings indicator (ROE) and prime financial health indicator (SR) of the non-life insurers.

Table 6.5 shows the variation of independent variables in the sample.

Table: 6.5: MANOVA Test of Model I of Non-Life Insurers (Pillai Test Statistic)

	Df	Test statistic	approx F	num Df	den Df	Pr(>F)
CER	1	0.57474	2.0272	2	3	0.27732 ⁱ
OER	1	0.32431	0.7200	2	3	0.55541 ⁱ
FDIR	1	0.02826	0.0436	2	3	0.95791 ⁱ
GRR	1	0.47035	1.3320	2	3	0.38547 ⁱ
AIY	1	0.92180	17.6816	2	3	0.02187 ^{**}

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. ** marked value indicates significant (acceptance) at 5% level
- ii. *i* marked values indicate insignificant (non-acceptance)

Table 6.5 shows that test statistic of the all variables (except AIY) are insignificant. So, no variations in the mean of variables CER, OER, FDIR, and GRR are present in this sample. Therefore, no direct conclusion on the impact of FDI inflows on ROE and SR can be arrived. Hence, we can apply Model 2, where the independent variable FDIR is excluded to judge whether FDI have any effect on the ROE and SR or not.

6.4 MODEL 2: MULTIVARIATE REGRESSION ANALYSIS (MVRA) OF NON- LIFE INSURERS WITHOUT FDI INFLOWS

Table 6.6 shows MVRA of two dependent variables ROE and SR with four independent variables CER, OER, GRR, and AIY (i.e., the exclusion of FDIR).

Table: 6.6: Coefficients of MVRA of ROE and SR of Non-Life Insurers (without FDIR)

Response ROE				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.1236	1.0930	-0.113	0.91437 ⁱ
CER	4.2586	3.1583	1.348	0.23539 ⁱ
OER	-2.9549	1.7586	-1.680	0.15374 ⁱ
GRR	-0.4326	0.9696	-0.446	0.67416 ⁱ
AIY	34.8400	7.0487	4.943	0.00431 ^{**}
Residual standard error: 0.07128 on 5 degrees of freedom Multiple R-squared: 0.9186, Adjusted R-squared: 0.8534 F-statistic: 7.0487 14.1 on 4 and 5 DF, p-value: 0.006239				
Response SR				
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	8.164	2.580	3.164	0.025 ^{**}
CER	-4.989	7.456	-0.669	0.533 ⁱ
OER	-4.132	4.152	-0.995	0.365 ⁱ
GRR	-3.992	2.289	-1.744	0.142 ⁱ
AIY	-25.527	16.640	-1.534	0.186 ⁱ
Residual standard error: 0.1683 on 5 degrees of freedom Multiple R-squared: 0.7779, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6002 F-statistic: 4.377 on 4 and 5 DF, p-value: 0.06848				

Source: Computed

Notes:

- i. ** marked values indicate significant (acceptance) at 5% level
- ii. *i* marked values indicate insignificant(non-acceptance)

From Table 6.6, it is observed that in response to ROE, the co-efficient of all the independent variables (except AIY) are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of the 4th null hypothesis (H_{O4} : FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers). For AIY, it is significant which leads to the rejection of the 4th null hypothesis. Since all the independent variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on ROE.

In response to SR, the co-efficient of all the independent variables are insignificant which leads to the acceptance of 4th null hypothesis (H_{O4} : FDI inflow in Private

insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurers). Since all the variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on SR. Thus, in both the cases, FDI inflow does not put any significant impact on the prime earnings indicator (ROE) and prime financial health indicator (SR) of the non-life insurers.

Figure 6.3 and 6.4 shows the graphical representation of all the independent variables in response to ROE and SR with the inclusion of FDIR as independent variable and exclusion of FDIR as independent variable to show the effect of FDIR.

Figure 6.3: Coefficient Plot of Model-1 Non-Life Insurers with FDIR

Source: Computed

Figure 6.3 shows the shaded part of non- acceptance region where all the independent variables (except AIY) lies on that part. So, it can be concluded that the FDIR have no special impact on ROE and SR. The variables (except AIY) perfectly lies within the confidence limit i.e., these variables has no impact on the earnings indicator and financial health indicator of the non-life insurers i.e., they are not significantly different from the weight of null hypothesis i.e., 0.

Figure 6.4: Coefficient Plot of Model-1- Non-Life Insurers without FDIR

Figure 6.4 depicts the shaded part of non-acceptance region where all the independent variable lies except AIY. Since all the variables are not outside on that part, it can be concluded that FDIR have no special impact on ROE and SR. Thus, only AIY is significant when regression is run without FDI inflow variable. Other variables also appeared to be insignificant.

CHAPTER- 7

SUMMARIES, CONCLUSIONS, AND SUGGESTIONS

Chapter Outline:

- 7.1 *Summary of Chapter 1 (Introduction)***
- 7.2 *Summary of Chapter 2 (Literature Review)***
- 7.3 *Summary of Chapter 3 (Research Methodology)***
- 7.4 *Summary of Chapter 4 (FDI in Insurance Sector: An Overview)***
- 7.5 *Summary of Chapter 5 (Financial Performance of Private Life and Non-Life Insurers: A Comparative Analysis)***
- 7.6 *Summary of Chapter 6 (FDI in Insurance Sector: Impact on Financial Performance of Private Life and Non-Life Insurers)***
- 7.7 *Overall Conclusion***
- 7.8 *Suggestions/Recommendations for Improvement of the Performance of the Private Insurers***
- 7.9 *Limitations of the Study***
- 7.10 *Scope for Further Research***

Chapter – 7 Summaries, Conclusions, and Suggestions

In this chapter, chapter-wise summary and overall conclusion of the study are given along with suggestions, limitations, and added scope of research of the study.

7.1 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 1 (INTRODUCTION)

In this chapter, an introductory idea about financial assessment and insurance sector has been discussed. Apart from it, role of IRDA, investment of insurers, idea of private insurers and FDI in private insurance sector have also been stated in this chapter. Lastly, research problem has been identified in the penultimate part of this chapter.

The summary of this chapter are as follows:

1. After 1947, life insurance business in India was wholly nationalized on January 1956 and the Life Insurance Corporation Act was passed by the Parliament. In the non- life insurance sector, General Insurance Business Act of 1972 was approved by the Indian Parliament through amalgamation of 107 general insurance companies operating on that time and formed four companies in the Government sector.
2. In the year 1999, the Government of India formed a sole regulating body in the name of Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI) by passing an Act in the Parliament. IRDAI is the apex regulator that supervises the insurance sector.
3. In India, insurance industry has 57 insurance companies, where 24 are in the life insurance sector and 34 are in the non-life insurance sector. Among all the life insurers, only LIC, the public insurer and the remaining 23 companies are private insurers. In the non-life insurance segment, there are 6 public sector insurers in the non-life insurance segment and the rest 28 are private insurers.
4. IRDAI provides rules in the areas of protecting the interests of the policyholder, registration for new insurance companies, guarantee persistent with development of both the insurers and the policyholder, audits of insurance companies to control over misconducts, training of insurance agents, monitoring the investment of funds by insurance companies and code of conduct to be followed by surveyors and loss assessors.

5. IRDAI published regulations in the year 2000 which notified the ceiling of investment to be made by the life and non-life insurers in exercising of the powers conferred in the Insurance Act, 1938.
6. The access road of allowing private insurance companies in India had formalized in the year 1999 through the Insurance Regulatory and Development Act, 1999 (IRD Act). The IRDAI opened up the market for private players in August 2000 with formal invitation for application to get registration in life and non-life insurance business.
7. In the year 2000, after the representation of the IRDA Act, 1999 legalized the inflow of foreign shareholding (commonly known as FDI) only in the private life and non-life insurance companies to the extent of 26 per cent of the total shareholding. In the year 2015, the Government of India hiked the FDI capital in the private life and non-life insurers from 26 per cent to 49 per cent.
8. FDI in insurance sector would be able to escalate the penetration of insurance in India and it can also be able to meet the long term capital requirements to fund the building of infrastructures in India. IRDA as the sole regulator of insurance sector is in support for an increase in foreign equity capital through FDI inflows in the areas of insurance joint ventures, especially in the private sector insurers. The present study makes an attempt to assess the financial performance in terms of return on equity, solvency, commission, operating expenses ratios, insured volumes and investment behaviour of the private sector insurers in the liberalized FDI inflows in life and non- life insurance in India. In addition, the study also evaluates the potency of FDI to increase profitability of the private sector insurers covering both life and non- life insurance or any one of them.

7.2 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 2 (LITERATURE REVIEW)

The obtainable Indian and Foreign literatures on the financial assessment of life insurers and non-life insurers that existed from various sources are reviewed in this chapter and accordingly research gaps have been identified.

1. Few studies carried out on LICI on divisional performance, service quality, customer satisfaction, agent's performance, insurance penetration, and market share considering only Government insurers.

2. Few studies work out on financial performance on life insurers taking both private sector and Government sector on post-liberalization era in respect of profitability performance. Some studies carried out on comparative financial analysis on Government and private life insurers.
3. Many studies carried out on non-life insurers in respect of regulatory issues, productivity, efficiency and service cost.
4. Few studies carried out comparative analysis of private life and non-life insurers along with U.S based companies.
5. Few studies carried out on the impact of FDI policies on life and non-life insurance companies, impact analysis on specific private insurance companies and also made comparison on FDI based and non-FDI based non-life insurance companies.
6. Few studies considered both life and non- life insurance companies in respect of communication channels, privatization of insurance companies and impact on FDI by taking into consideration of the policies sold by the Government and private sector insurers in very specific areas.

From the appraisal of literatures as declared above, the following gaps have been identified:

Majority of the studies have been carried out in the context of only insurance penetration of life or non- life or both insurers after the implementation of FDI approvals and assess impact of the same between Public and Private Insurers, although FDI inflows are not yet permissible in the public insurance sector in India. Most of the previous studies have focused on the performance assessment with respect to profitability on few selected indicators and a small number of studies empirically tested the effect of FDI hike in life and non-life insurance sectors at aggregative level. Very few studies have focused on the service management of the private insurance sectors during FDI periods in the context of number of insurance policies issued, insurance penetration and status of grievances linked with financial performance. Few studies are attempted to analyze the growth of investment behavior and investment income of private life and non-life insurance companies at aggregative level during the FDI period.

Hence, the present study may be considered as an initial attempt to study the financial assessment of private life and non-life insurers at aggregative level in the context of

earnings indicator, financial health indicator, investment behavior and service linked revenue indicator.

7.3 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 3 (RESEARCH METHODOLOGY)

On the basis of the research gap as stated in Chapter 2, the primary objective set in this study is to compare and assess the financial performance in terms of profitability, solvency, investment behaviour and service management of private sector insurers that are regulated by IRDA in Life and Non-Life Insurance at aggregative level with reference to FDI in India. To attain the objectives of the study, the following testable null hypotheses have been formulated:

1. H_{O1}: There has been no significant growth in selected financial performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurance companies.
2. H_{O2}: There is no significant difference in average financial performance with respect to selected performance parameters between private Life and Non-Life Insurance companies.
3. H_{O3}: There is no significant impact on selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurance companies due to substantial FDI hike that took place during the period under study.
4. H_{O4}: FDI inflow in Private insurance sector has no significant impact on the selected performance parameters of private Life and Non-Life Insurance companies.

On the basis of availability of data, aggregate figures of only private life and non-life insurance companies in India for a period of 10 years from the financial year 2010-11 to the financial year 2019-20 have been chosen that are registered with IRDA, which also forms the sample size of our study. The data have been collected mainly from secondary sources. For our data scrutiny, the followings tools and techniques have been intentionally used.

1. To calculate the trend growth rate of selected performance indicators (aggregative), semi-log regression model has been applied in the study since it gives the growth rate directly at a point of time.
2. Since the sample size is less than 30, we have employed Fisher's t Test to test the difference of mean of selected performance indicators between life insurers (aggregative) and non-life insurers (aggregative).

3. Chow test is used to determine whether a single regression for private life and non-life insurers is more efficient than two separate regressions during pre and post-hiked FDI periods involving splitting of the data into two sub-samples on the basis of FDI ceiling. This indicates whether in the second case, we have a structural break at 't' point of time or not. The null hypothesis in this model is the structural stability due to hike in FDI ceiling.
4. Multivariate Regression Analysis is used as a linear regression which accommodates more than one independent variable for life and non-life insurers. This equation finds association between the dependent variable and each independent variable, while calculating for all other variables. The impact of FDI has been judged with this model on the dependent variable Return on Equity (ROE) and Solvency Ratio (SR) of life and non-life insurers at aggregate level.

7.4 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 4 (FDI IN INSURANCE SECTOR: AN OVERVIEW)

In this chapter, the route, ceiling eligibility, and conditions of FDI investment in private insurance sector have been defined.

1. In India, the insurance sector specific ceiling of approval in respect to the automatic route of FDI is specified under the consolidated FDI Policy.
2. The eligible investor of FDI must be non-resident except citizen of Bangladesh and Pakistan. NRIs resident and citizens of Nepal and Bhutan are permitted to invest and entities having adverse notice of RBI are not able to make new investments. A company, trust, and partnership firm incorporated outside India and owned and controlled by NRIs is able to invest in India in accordance with the special dispensation rules under FDI Policy.
3. Investee entities under FDI must be an Indian Company. A Person of Indian Origin (PIO) or a Non-Resident Indian (NRI) residing outside India can invest in the capital of a firm or a proprietary concern in India on repatriation basis i.e., not in automatic route.
4. The ceiling of equity investment by the eligible investors in the eligible investees for the life and non-life insurance companies is 26% before Insurance Laws (Amendment) Act 2015 and after that, it is 49%.

5. A PIO) or NRI willing to invest in the insurance sector not covered under automatic route of investment are required to pursue an application with all prescribed documents to RBI to get aforementioned permission of FDI investment in any sole proprietorship concerns or partnership firms engaged in insurance activities. This process is known as repatriation option of investment in FDI.
6. Any person who is a resident of outside India not covered under NRIs/PIO category may sort for an application of FDI investment in insurance sector need to get prior approval from RBI. These persons need to follow the procedure of investment covered under repatriation option of investment in FDI. In this case, the permission also grant with consultation between Government of India and the appropriate authorities engaged for that purpose.
7. The Central Government has also notified the Indian Insurance Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015 which mainly administer Indian control over Indian Insurance Company. According to this rule, control in Indian ownership includes shareholding, management rights, shareholders agreements, and voting agreements in Indian Private Sector Companies.
8. The guidelines of “Indian Owned and Controlled” as stated in Indian Insurance Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015 are the directors excluding independent directors and should be appointed though direct nomination by the Indian investor and chairman should be nominated by the Indian investor. For all the meetings, quorum means and includes presence of majority of the Indian directors irrespective of whether a foreign investor’s nominee is present or not. The right of a nominee of Foreign Investor’s is to constitute a valid quorum for meetings with a protective right and to that extent that it would not amount to control within the meaning. A certified copy of the joint venture agreement should be prepared in accordance with the said rules. The Intermediaries of insurance companies as defined in the IRDA Act, 1999 such as Brokers, Third Party Administrators, Surveyors and Loss Assessors etc. having more than 50% of its revenue from the insurance activities shall have to follow rules of Indian Insurance Companies (Foreign Investment) Rules, 2015, if foreign investment is invited.

7.5 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 5 (FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURERS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS)

In this chapter, a comparative financial performance associated with the parameters i.e., earning indicator, financial health indicator, investment behavior and revenue linked service indicator between private life insurers and private non-life insurers have been analyzed at aggregate level.

1. As per IRDA (Investment) Regulations, 2000, every private life and non-life insurer is required to follow the ceiling of investments from their available funds of investment. This ceiling is different for the private life insurers and the private non-life insurers. It is observed that the growth rate of all the financial instruments are positive and significant for both life and non-life insurers during the study period. However, the growth rate of investment income and annualized investment yield of the life insurers are negative, although insignificant and it is positive and statistically significant for the non-life insurers.
2. It is observed that the difference between the performances of the private life and non- life insurers in terms of investment income is significant at 1% probability level. On the other hand, in terms of annualized investment yield, the difference between the performance of private life and non-life insurers is insignificant.
3. In respect of the earnings and financial health indicators, life insurers shows positive growth rate in ROE and FDIR, although, the result is significant for FDIR and insignificant for ROE. Furthermore, for life insurers, OER and SR show significant negative growth, while CER reveals insignificant negative growth. Non-life insurers reveal an affirmative growth rate in ROE, CER, and FDIR, although the result is significant for CER and FDIR. The ROE growth rate is positive, although it is insignificant. Moreover, for non-life insurers, OER and SR show insignificant negative growth during the period of study.
4. It is observed that the difference between the performances of the private life and non- life insurers in terms of earnings indicator ROE and financial health indicator FDIR are insignificant. On the other hand, the difference between the performance of the private life and non- life insurers in terms of earnings

indicator (i.e., CER and OR) and financial health indicator (SR) are significant.

5. Chow test is used to measure the differences in financial growth of the private life and non-life insurers in India during the study period. For life insurers, it reveals insignificant results for ROE and OER, which indicates that there has been no significant change due to the hike of ceiling in FDI during the study period. However, the results are found to be significant for CER, SR, and FDIR, which implies that there is a significant change in these parameters due to the hike of ceiling in FDI.

For non-life insurers, an unimportant results are observed for ROE, OER, SR, and FDIR, which indicates that there has been no significant change in these parameters due to hike of ceiling in FDI during the study period. However, significant result is observed for CER, which indicates that there is important change in the growth rates of CER.

6. To arrive at a definite conclusion, we run two regression equations and the estimated beta coefficients of the respective equations are applied in the Chow test. The first equation takes ROE as dependent variable and the independent variables are represented by CER, OER, and FDIR. In the second regression equation, the dependent variable is represented by SR and the independent variable is represented by FDIR. For life insurers, it is found that Chow F Statistic value of ROE and SR is insignificant. For non-life insurers, it shows insignificant results for both ROE and SR. Thus, it indicates that there has been no alteration in growth rates of the selected fiscal performance indicators due to hike in FDI ceiling for both life and non-life insurers during the study period.
7. In respect to the revenue linked service indicator for life insurers, it shows insignificant growth in respect of new policies issued. However, the growth rate of new grievances reported in respect to the services is negative, although found to be insignificant. For non-life insurers, it shows that the number of policies newly issued is positive and significant. However, the growth rate of new grievances reported in respect of policies issued is found to be positive, although insignificant.
8. The average grievances resolved ratios by the both life and non-life insurers are satisfactory as it is over 98%. But, if we compare ratio between life and

non-life insurers, then we find that the performance of grievance resolved ratios by the life insurers are slightly better than that of the non-life insurers with lower standard deviation.

9. For life insurers, a highlighting declining trend is observed from the year 2014-15 to 2019-20. So, the changes in the ceiling of FDI inflows from 2014-15 may have an effect in the service quality of the life insurers. The minimum number of grievances reported can be treated as outcome of better service quality by the life insurers. On the other hand, for the non-life insurers, the changes in the ceiling of FDI inflows and changes in the management thereof can't have positive impact on the service quality. A mixed observation is located in the declining trend of new grievances reported by the non-life insurers during the period of study.

7.6 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 6 (FDI IN INSURANCE SECTOR: IMPACT ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE LIFE AND NON-LIFE INSURERS)

In this chapter, impact of FDI inflows on the financial performance parameters of the private Life and Non-Life insurers have been analyzed at aggregate level.

ROE and SR can be regarded as prime financial indicator of the insurers in terms of profitability. The other earnings indicators (i.e., CER, OER, GRR, AIY, and FDIR) also have impact on ROE and SR. Here, the effect of FDIR is to be noticed on these variables to analyze the impact of FDI inflows on ROE and SR. For that purpose, Multivariate Regression Analysis (MRVA) has been applied with two dependent variables (i.e., ROE and SR) and five independent variables (i.e., CER, OER, GRR, AIY and FDIR) as per data.

1. MVRA of life insurers at aggregate level with consideration of FDIR reveals for ROE that the co-efficient of the independent variables CER, OER, FDIR, and AIY are insignificant. Only one independent variable (i.e., GRR) is significant. In response to SR, the co-efficient of all the independent variables (i.e., CER, OER, FDIR, AIY, and GRR) are insignificant. Thus, in both the cases, FDI inflows does not put any significant impact on the prime earnings indicator (represented by ROE) and prime financial health indicator (represented by SR) of the life insurance companies.

2. MVRA of life insurers at aggregate level without consideration of FDIR reveals for ROE that the co-efficient of all the independent variables are insignificant. In response to SR, the co-efficient of the independent variables (i.e., GRR and AIY) are insignificant and co-efficient of CER and OER are significant. Since all the variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on ROE and SR.
3. MVRA of non-life insurers at aggregate level with consideration of FDIR reveals in response to ROE that the co-efficient of the independent variables (i.e., CER, OER, FDIR, and GRR) are insignificant. Only one independent variable (i.e., AIY) is significant. In response to SR, the co-efficient of all the independent variables represented by CER, OER, FDIR, AIY, and GRR are insignificant. Since all the independent variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on ROE and SR for non-life insurers during the study period.
4. MVRA of non-life insurers at aggregate level without consideration of FDIR reveals in response to ROE, that the co-efficient of all the independent variables (except AIY) are insignificant. For AIY, it is significant. In response to SR, the co-efficient of all the independent variables are insignificant. Since all the variables are not significant, it can be concluded that FDI inflows have no significant impact on ROE and SR.

7.7 OVERALL CONCLUSION

In line of the different ceiling of investment instruments guided by IRDA in respect of the private life and non-life insurer, it is found that growth rate of all the investment instruments are positive and insignificant during the study period. But the investment income and annualized investment yield (AIY) of the life insurers are negative though insignificant. On the other hand, it is positive and significant for non-life insurers. So, the investment management performance of private non-life insurers is better than that of the private life insurers. The difference of the mean investment income between life and non-life insurers is significant, although insignificant for AIY.

Financial assessment in terms of prime earnings indicator and financial health indicator of life and non-life insurers, ROE (Return on Equity) shows positive but insignificant growth and SR (Solvency Ratio) shows negative significant growth

which can't be treated as a favourable situation. However, OER (Operating Expenses Ratio) shows negative growth and FDIR (FDI inflow Ratio) growth is positive and significant, both of which is desirable. It is also noticed that CER (Commission Expenses Ratio) growth is higher for life insurers than that of the non-life insurers which reveals higher surplus for life insurance policy holders. The difference of mean of the performance indicator between life and non-life insurers in respect of ROE and FDIR are insignificant i.e., no difference in growth. However, for CER, OER, and SR, it is significant i.e., difference exists in growth.

From the year 2015, the changes in the FDI ceiling from 26% to 49% leads to the change in the structural break in the equity management and administration part for both life and non-life insurers and for that purpose, the difference in growth rates of the two sub periods has been analyzed. To get an overall idea, two regression equations have been formulated for two prime indicators i.e., ROE and SR as dependent variable and other earnings and financial health parameters as independent variable. The result is insignificant for both life and non-life insurers. So, the ceiling change in the FDI has hardly any affect in the performance indicators.

In terms of revenue linked service indicator with respect to number of policies issued, the growth rate is better for non-life insurers than that of the life insurers since its growth is significant. The GRR (Grievances Resolved ratio) for both the insurers are desirable and almost 100%. But the changes in the ceiling of FDI and the change of management thereof shows a declining trend for life insurers from 2015. However, it has hardly any affect for non-life insurers.

To get an overall idea to judge the impact of FDI for life and non-life insurers, Multivariate Regression Analysis (MRVA) has been performed with the inclusion of FDIR and exclusion of FDIR on prime performance parameter represented by ROE and SR. It shows insignificant results for both the insurers i.e., FDI have no impact on these parameters during the study period.

Finally to conclude, it has been observed from the study that growth in the difference parameters is not desirable for both the insurers. The changes in the ceiling of FDI inflows and the overall impact of FDI during the study period on the performance parameter shows unsatisfactory results i.e., no impact is found for both the private life and non-life insurers. Somehow, in terms of investment management, a marginal better result is found for the non-life insurers.

7.8 SUGGESTIONS/RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF THE PRIVATE INSURERS

1. The value of investment in the various instruments within the ceiling of IRDA has been increased for life insurers, but the investment income and annualized yield has not increased accordingly. So, the life insurers should keep in mind the effective investment management in their future periods to get better results.
2. The solvency ratio in terms of income over debt obligation has been disclosed in the IRDA report. Therefore, solvency in terms of debt and equity should be disclosed in the report.
3. The new grievances reporting for both life and non-life insurers are very high in terms of their numbers. Therefore, service quality to the policy holders should be improved for both the insurers.
4. Region-wise reporting should be made by the IRDA to assess the insurance penetration properly.
5. Insurance penetration for the rural areas and urban areas as compared to the population should be made by the IRDA in their annual report in order to judge the performance in micro way.
6. The changes in the FDI inflows results the changes in the management and their operating style and the operating expenses has been managed properly. However, financial performance of the private insurer has not improved. So, the consideration of hike in FDI inflows should be re-examined.
7. The overall performance of both the life insurers in terms of their own profitability has not shown favourable results. Hence, FDI have hardly any effect on the financial performance. Therefore, offering for new company-wise FDI to reach the maximum ceiling of IRDA needs to be reconsidered in the forthcoming periods.
8. The changes in the management due to FDI and their performance should be improved to get better results.
9. Company-wise performance of life and non-life insurers in terms of financial parameters should be disclosed by IRDA.

10. The companies having lower volume of FDI inflows should rethink for enhancement of the same, since it may have positive impact to increase their profitability after enhancement.

7.9 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The study is based on secondary data. So, it may have all the restrictions that are intrinsic with secondary data.
2. The financial assessment to judge only for the parameters beneficial for the insurers have been considered, but their effect on the policy holder's benefit has not been analyzed due to non-availability of data.
3. The external debt- equity position in terms of the long term solvency of the insurers at aggregate level is not considered due to non- availability of data.
4. The study is based on a small sample, although it is sufficient for the analysis of our study.

7.10 SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

1. The study can be carried out over an extended time period that will comprise some more important characteristics of time series data, like variations in the FDI inflows from its implementation.
 2. The study can be carried out with a larger sample, allowing the investigator to overcome the problems normally related with small samples.
 3. Company-wise analysis may be carried out subject to availability of data. This type of analysis may expose the role of individual performance indicator in terms of FDI inflows contributing to the variances in the altitudes of performances of the private life and non-life insurers.
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Appendix -A
List of Private Sector Insurers Registered with IRDAI
as on 31st March 2020

Private Life Insurers

1. Aditya Birla Sun Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
2. Aegon Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
3. Aviva Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
4. Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
5. Bharti AXA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
6. Canara HSBC OBC Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
7. Edleweiss Tokio Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
8. Exide Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
9. Future Generali Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
10. HDFC Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
11. ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
12. IDBI Federal Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
13. India First Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
14. Kotak Mahindra Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
15. Max Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
16. PNB Met Life India Insurance Co. Ltd.
17. Pramerica Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
18. Reliance Nippon Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
19. Sahara Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
20. SBI Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
21. Shriram Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
22. Star Union Dai-ichi Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
23. TATA AIA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.

Private Non-Life Insurers

1. Acko General Insurance Ltd.
2. Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Co. Ltd.
3. Bharti AXA General Insurance Co. Ltd.
4. Cholamandalam MS General Insurance Co. Ltd.

Appendix –A- Contd.
Private Non-Life Insurers- Contd.

5. Edelweiss General Insurance Co. Ltd.
6. Future Generali India Insurance Co. Ltd.
7. Go Digit General Insurance Limited
8. HDFC ERGO General insurance Co. Ltd.
9. ICICI Lombard General Insurance Co. Ltd.
10. IFFCO TOKIO General Insurance Co. Ltd.
11. Kotak Mahindra General Insurance Co. Ltd.
12. Liberty General Insurance Limited.
13. Magma HDI General Insurance Co. Ltd.
14. NAVI General Insurance Limited
15. Raheja QBE General Insurance Co. Ltd.
16. Reliance General Insurance Co. Ltd.
17. Royal Sundaram General Insurance Co. Ltd.
18. SBI General Insurance Co. Ltd.
19. Shriram General Insurance Co. Ltd.
20. Tata AIG General Insurance Co. Ltd.
21. Universal Sompo General Insurance Co. Ltd.
22. Agricultural Insurance Company of India Ltd.
23. ECGC Ltd.
24. Aditya Birla Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
25. HDFC ERGO Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
26. ManipalCigna Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
27. Max Bupa Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
28. Religare Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
29. Star Health & Allied Insurance Co. Ltd.
30. Reliance Health Insurance Ltd.

Appendix -B
Proportion of FDI inflows of Private Sector Insurers
Registered with IRDAI as on 31st March 2020

Private Life Insurers

<i>Name</i>	<i>FDI (%)</i>
1. Aditya Birla Sun Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
2. Aegon Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
3. Aviva Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
4. Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	26
5. Bharti AXA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
6. Canara HSBC OBC Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	26
7. Edleweiss Tokio Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
8. Exide Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
9. Future Generali Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
10. HDFC Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	34.23
11. ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	37.68
12. IDBI Federal Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	26
13. India First Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	27.17
14. Kotak Mahindra Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
15. Max Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	25.48
16. PNB Met Life India Insurance Co. Ltd.	32.05
17. Pramerica Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
18. Reliance Nippon Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
19. Sahara Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
20. SBI Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	40.19
21. Shriram Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	42.39
22. Star Union Dai-ichi Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	45.94
23. TATA AIA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.	49

Appendix –B- Contd.**Private Non-Life Insurers**

<i>Name</i>	<i>FDI (%)</i>
1. Acko General Insurance Ltd.	Nil
2. Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Co. Ltd.	26
3. Bharti AXA General Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
4. Cholamandalam MS General Insurance Co. Ltd.	40
5. Edelweiss General Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
6. Future Generali India Insurance Co. Ltd.	25.51
7. Go Digit General Insurance Limited	Nil
8. HDFC ERGO General insurance Co. Ltd.	48.23
9. ICICI Lombard General Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
10. IFFCO TOKIO General Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
11. Kotak Mahindra General Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
12. Liberty General Insurance Limited.	48.68
13. Magma HDI General Insurance Co. Ltd.	22.26
14. NAVI General Insurance Limited.	Nil
15. Raheja QBE General Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
16. Reliance General Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
17. Royal Sundaram General Insurance Co. Ltd.	40
18. SBI General Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
19. Shriram General Insurance Co. Ltd.	22.92
20. Tata AIG General Insurance Co. Ltd.	26
21. Universal Sompo General Insurance Co. Ltd.	34.61
22. Agricultural Insurance Company of India Ltd.	Nil
23. ECGC Ltd.	Nil
24. Aditya Birla Health Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
25. HDFC ERGO Health Insurance Co. Ltd.	48.43
26. Manipal Cigna Health Insurance Co. Ltd.	49
27. Max Bupa Health Insurance Co. Ltd.	44.42
28. Religare Health Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
29. Star Health & Allied Insurance Co. Ltd.	Nil
30. Reliance Health Insurance Ltd.	Nil

Appendix –C

List of Publications from the Post-Doctoral research Work

1. Basu, Tamal and Aithal, P.S. (2022). Financial Growth Assessment of Private Life Insurers in India: An Aggregative Study. *Revista Review Index Journal of Multidisciplinary* , Vol.2, No.3, Issue -Jul-Sep 2022, pp.6-13.
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